

EAGER

tEchnologies And techniques for satcom beyond 5G nEtwoRks

White Paper

Architectures, services, and technologies towards
6G Non-Terrestrial Networks

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The first global standard for Satellite Communications (SatCom) was published in April 2022 as an outcome of 3GPP Rel. 17. It specifies the features enabling 5G systems to support a non-terrestrial component. More than technical specifications, it also enables the integration of the satellite industry in the 3GPP ecosystem, involving more than 700 organizations at worldwide level to ensure a global market.

The 3GPP work in Rel.18 has already started as part of 5G-Advanced which will introduce several enhancing features to further improve the performances and/or to provide brand new capabilities. Moreover, the discussion on the contents of Rel. 19 for satellite-enabling features has already started in the service requirement working group of 3GPP.

In this framework, it is absolutely timely to undertake a study on the technologies and techniques for the non-terrestrial component as part of 5G-Advanced (3GPP Rel.18 onward) and Beyond 5G (B5G) so as to define and develop the next of 3GPP-defined Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) enhancements.

In fact, while the current Rel. 17 NTN standard provides a solid ground for future satellite networks integrated in the 5G system, a significant innovation breakthrough in technologies, techniques, and architectures is needed to prepare for next generation satellite networks based on Rel. 19 and beyond NTN standards, [1]-[2].

In this White Paper, we first discuss the path that led to the definition of the first set of specifications for NTN-based 5G systems in Rel. 17 and then provide an overview of the current activities, as well as what can be considered as candidate architectures and technologies, for 5G-Advanced and 6G NTN systems. The analyses and assessments reported in this document are currently being performed in the framework of the ESA Project EAGER (tEchnologies And techniques for satcom beyond 5G nEtwoRks), in which both mid-term (5G and 5G-Advanced) and long-term (6G) solutions for NTN systems are evaluated.

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ABBREVIATIONS

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5G-A	5G-Advanced
ACIR	Adjacent Channel Interference Ratio
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMF	Access and Mobility Function
ATG	Air-To-Ground
AR	Augmented Reality
B5G	Beyond 5G
BWP	Bandwidth Part
CA	Carrier Aggregation
CF-MIMO	Cell Free MIMO
CT	Core network and Terminals
CP	Control Plane
CPRI	Common Public Radio Interface
CSI	Channel State Information
DC	Dual Connectivity
DD	Delay-Doppler
DL	Downlink
eMBB	enhanced Mobile Broadband
eMBB-s	eMBB via satellite
EMF	Electromagnetic Field
eMTC	enhanced Machine Type Communications
ESIM	Earth Station in Motion
FDD	Frequency Division Duplexing
FG-NET-2030	ITU-T Focus Group Technologies for Network 2030
FR	Frequency Range
GEO	Geostationary Earth Orbit
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GSO	Geosynchronous Orbit
GW	Gateway
HAPS	High Altitude Platform Station
HARQ	Hybrid Automatic Repeat request
HD	High Definition
HPUE	High Power UE
HRC-s	High Reliability Communications via satellite
HTA	Heavier-Than-Air UAS
IAB	Integrated Access and Backhaul
IMT	International Mobile Telecommunications
IoT	Internet of Things
IPTV	Internet Protocol Television
ITU	International Telecommunications Union
KPI	Key Performance Requirement
LEO	Low Earth Orbit
LTA	Lighter-Than-Air UAS
MAC	Medium Access Control

MBS	Multicast and Broadcast Services
MC	Multi-Connectivity
MEO	Medium Earth Orbit
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
mMTC-s	mMTC via satellite
ML	Machine Learning
MN	Master Node
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MR-DC	Multi-Ratio DC
MSS	Mobile Satellite Service
MT	Mobile Termination
NB-IoT	Narrowband IoT
NFV	Network Function Virtualisation
NGSO	Non-Geosynchronous Orbit
NOMA	Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access
NR	New Radio
NSA	Non-Standalone
NT	Non-Terrestrial
NTN	Non-Terrestrial Network
OBP	On-Board Processor
O-RAN	Open-RAN
OTFS	Orthogonal Time Frequency Space
PAPR	Peak-to-Average-Power Ratio
PDCP	Packet Data Convergence Protocol
PDU	Protocol Data Unit
PHY	Physical layer
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RA	Random Access
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
RF	Radio Frequency
RIS	Reflecting Intelligent Surface
RLC	Radio Link Control
RRC	Radio Resource Control
RRM	Radio Resource Management
SA	Service and system Aspects
SAN	Satellite Access Node
SatCom	Satellite Communications
SDAP	Service Data Adaptation Protocol
SDN	Software Defined Network
SDR	Software Defined Radio
SI	Study Item
SN	Secondary Node
SNG	Satellite News Gathering
SNO	Satellite Network Operator

SoA	State-of-the-Art
SRI	Satellite Radio Interface
SUL	Supplementary UL
TA	Timing Advance
TDD	Time Division Duplexing
TN	Terrestrial Network
TSG	Technical Specification Group
UAS	Unmanned Aircraft System
UHD	Ultra HD
UL	Uplink
UP	User Plane
UPF	User Plane Function
URLLC	Ultra Reliable and Low Latency Communications
VR	Virtual Reality
VSAT	Very Small Aperture Terminal
WG	Working Group
WI	Work Item

1 3GPP NORMATIVE WORK FOR NTN IN REL. 17 AND BEYOND

The added value of the integration of a Non-Terrestrial (NT) segment in the New Radio (NR) architecture was recognized by 3GPP since Rel. 15, aiming at, [3]: i) complementing 5G services in under-/un-served areas and resolving the “0G” issue; ii) improving the 5G service reliability and continuity for massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC), Internet of Things (IoT) devices, or for Mission Critical services; and iii) improving the 5G network scalability by means of efficient multicast/broadcast resources for data delivery. In the timeframe 2017/2019, Rel.15 and Rel. 16 Study Items (SIs), *i.e.*, pre-normative work, under Technical Specification Group (TSG) Radio Access Network (RAN) and Service and system Aspects (SA) related to the use of satellite access in 5G and the support of NR for NTN paved the way for the approval of the first dedicated NTN Work Item (WI) in December 2019. This represented a turning-point for the definition of a truly integrated NT component in the terrestrial 5G system, starting from Rel. 17 frozen in 2022.

The NTN standard is the result of a joint effort between stakeholders of both the mobile and satellite industries, leading to a two-fold benefit: i) the possibility to truly achieve global service continuity and resiliency, for 3GPP; and ii) the access to the unified and global 3GPP ecosystem and the possibility to reduce the costs through economy of scale, for the satellite industries. Moreover, before NTN, there was not inter-operable standard in SatCom; thus, the inclusion of a non-terrestrial component in 3GPP based systems can also lead to huge benefits for the SatCom industry as ground systems exploiting equipment coming from different providers are now available. This standard is also supported by vertical stakeholders (Public Safety, transportation, automotive, etc.) calling for: i) the seamless combination of satellite and mobile systems; and ii) the support of all 5G features across the access technologies. Such massive interest in the definition of the NTN standard is represented in Figure 1, showing the documents submitted to 3GPP grouped per TSG Working Group (WG): RAN, SA, and Core network and Terminals (CT)¹.

Figure 1. Cumulative number of documents related to NTN submitted to 3GPP meetings.

Figure 2 depicts the overall schedule of the SIs and WIs related to the standardisation of the features enabling 4G/5G systems to support a satellite component, also highlighting the leading TSG WG.

The NTN standard aims at supporting three general reference scenarios, which differ from each other in terms of targeted terminal types, operating band, service, and orbit, as reported in Table 1. In particular, we can distinguish between:

- satellite access networks operating in Frequency Range 1 (FR1), which provide direct wideband and narrowband connectivity to, respectively: i) outdoor handheld terminals and/or car/drone mounted devices, via the 5G NR standard; and ii) outdoor IoT devices, via the 4G NB-IoT/eMTC standard;
- satellite access networks operating in Frequency Range 2 (FR2), providing broadband connectivity to local access networks via Very Small Aperture Terminals (VSAT) installed on building rooftops or Earth Station In Motion (ESIM) terminals on moving platforms (vehicle, train, vessel, or airplane).

¹ The values reported in this figure have been obtained by web scraping the public information available on the 3GPP website in October, 2022, with a tool proprietary of the University of Bologna. As such, the exact values might be subject to variations, without impacting the general trends.

Figure 2. 3GPP NTN standardization schedule: Work and Study items on NTN.

Thanks to the relatively low altitude (between 500 and 1500 km) compared to Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO) at 35786 km or even Medium Earth Orbit (MEO) above 7000 km, Low Earth Orbit (LEO) based networks might allow to close the link budget with handheld terminals and feature a latency in line with that experienced in terrestrial 5G system. Hence, LEO networks can support both types of 5G NR scenarios.

Table 1: Targeted system scenarios defined in the 3GPP NTN standard.

	Direct connectivity (FR1)		Indirect connectivity (FR2)
Targeted terminals	IoT devices	handheld (smart phones) and car/drone mounted devices	VSAT and/or ESIM
Service	Narrowband hundreds of kbps	Wideband few Mbps	Broadband hundred Mbps
Orbit	GSO and NGSO	NGSO	GSO and NGSO
3GPP Radio interfaces	4G NB-IoT/eMTC	5G New Radio	5G New Radio
Market applications	Professional: utilities, agriculture	Consumer Professional: automotive, Public Safety, utilities, agriculture, Defense	Professional: telco (e.g., backhaul), IPTV, SNG, transportation, Public Safety, Defense

The 3GPP NTN standardisation activities took into account the specific characteristics of satellite networks and channels, which create new technical challenges compared to legacy terrestrial-only networks. More specifically, the NTN adaptations required to tackle issues related to the long propagation delays, large Doppler shifts and Doppler variations, and the generation of large moving cells on-ground to allow the exploitation of NTN links based on State-of-the-Art (SoA) space technologies and industrial assets. These are summarised in

Table 2.

The addressed NTN platforms include: i) GSO or NGSO spaceborne satellites; and ii) airborne vehicles operating at altitudes typically between 8 and 50 km, i.e., High Altitude Platform Stations (HAPS), encompassing Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS) including Lighter-Than-Air UAS (LTA) and Heavier-Than-Air UAS (HTA). In particular, 3GPP TR 38.811, [3], provided a solid background in terms of possible use cases, scenarios, and characterization of the NT channel; such characterisation included tackling the delay and Doppler variations, large latency and Doppler shift, differential delay and Doppler shift, the different propagation channel model, and the different radio unit performance due to the specific payload characteristics. In addition, TR 38.811 also provided a preliminary analysis related to the impact of bringing the NR Air Interface and protocols on NTN links.

Table 2: Satellite Network specific characteristics creating new technical issues compared to cellular networks, [3].

NTN characteristics	Technical issues	Impacted NR features	Potential areas of impact	Comments
Motion of the space/aerial vehicles	Moving cell pattern	Hand-over/paging	Higher layers impact	Paging and Hand-over procedures should be adapted to take into account the relative motion of the cell pattern with respect to the tracking area. Further analysis on tracking area design may need to be carried out. Mobility management is also to be considered.
	Delay variation	TA adjustment	Physical layer impact	Alignment of uplink signals may need to be considered.
	Doppler	Initial downlink synchronization	No impact	The preferred SCS values for Non-Terrestrial Networks may be respectively 60 KHz for frequency bands <6 GHz and 240 KHz for frequency bands > 6 GHz. However it can also operate with lower SCS value.
		DMRS time density	No impact	The preferred DM-RS configuration may be type 1 to cope with Doppler variation rate.
Altitude	Long latency	HARQ	Higher Layers & physical layer Impact	Need to adapt the HARQ specification. Deactivation and/or enhancements of NR HARQ can be considered.
		Physical layer Procedures (ACM, power control)	Physical layer impact	The operation/configuration of Adaptive power and coding/modulation control loop protocols may have to be adapted.
		MAC/RLC Procedures	Higher layers impact	Timers limit of MAC/RLC and higher layers loop protocols may have to be extended.
Cell size	Differential delay	TA in Random access response message	Physical layer impact	Doppler/Delay compensation technique can be implemented. Further analysis/simulations using the NTN channel model is needed. Adaptations of PRACH format and random access procedure may have to be considered.
		Random access	Physical layer impact	
Propagation channel	Impairments	DMRS frequency density	No impact	Non terrestrial network propagation channel may feature a frequency selective at most comparable with cellular channel.
	Impairments	Cyclic prefix	No impact	Non terrestrial network propagation channel may feature a worse delay spread at most comparable to cellular channels.
Duplex scheme	Regulatory constraints	Duplexing mode (TDD/FDD)	Higher layers impact	FDD is preferred especially for most satellite systems. TDD can be considered for HAPS and for LEO ^(*) .
Satellite or aerial Payload performance	Phase noise impairment	PT-RS	Potential constraint on the operation to be further studied	Satellite Radio links are typically operated with relatively low order modulation scheme, in most of the cases up to 16QAM.
	Back-off	PAPR	Physical layer impact	Uplink: It is recommended to use DFT-S OFDM Downlink: Low PAPR scheme may improve performance. However not mandatory to support non-terrestrial networks.

^(*) Note: there is one LEO network that operates in TDD mode (IridiumNext).

Building on these outcomes, 3GPP TR 38.821, [4], reports the identified NTN architectures for the NR RAN and a detailed analysis on the challenges and proposed solutions related to Layer 1 (e.g., physical layer procedures, including Random Access and Timing Advance), radio protocols (e.g., HARQ, mobility management in the Control Plane), and architecture and interfaces (e.g., tracking area management, management of the network identities).

In the following, we summarise the main protocol and architecture features for NTN in Rel. 17, [3]-[5].

1.1 NTN features in Release 17

NR system and NTN-based NG-RAN architecture

As shown in Figure 3, NT access is provided by means of an NTN payload, *i.e.*, a network node on-board a satellite, and an NTN Gateway (GW) interconnected by a feeder link to the payload and to the 5G Core network (5GC). In particular, the gNB is connected to the Access and Mobility Function (AMF) and the User Plane Function (UPF) for the Control Plane (CP) and User Plane (UP), respectively, through the NG Interface; as for the feeder link, considering that the payload is transparent and, thus, all protocols shall be terminated on-ground at the gNB, the Air Interface is the NR-Uu, which is also implemented on the service link to allow the User Equipment (UE) to access the NTN network services through the NTN payload. Despite a single gNB is represented in the figure, it shall be mentioned that a gNB might serve multiple NTN payloads, whereas an NTN payload might be served by multiple gNBs.

Figure 3. Overall illustration of an NTN based on transparent payload.

The transparent NTN payload forwards the radio protocols received from the UE (via the service link) to the NTN GW/gNB (via the feeder link) and *vice versa*. The following service links are supported:

- Earth-fixed beams: the beams continuously cover the same geographical area all the time (*e.g.*, GSO satellites);
- Quasi-Earth-fixed beams: the beams cover a geographical area for a limited period and a different area in the next limited period (*e.g.*, NGSO satellites generating steerable beams);
- Earth-moving beams: the beams cover a fixed area with respect to the satellite, *i.e.*, they are moving on the surface of the Earth along the satellite's movement on its orbit (*e.g.*, NGSO satellites generating non-steerable beams).

The NG-RAN is enhanced with features to support feeder link switch over, the handling of network identities, and neighbouring cell relations, especially when cells are moving on the ground (*i.e.*, Quasi-Earth-fixed beams and Earth-moving beams). To support the NTN access at system level, most of the standardisation effort was spent on the definition of new Quality of Service (QoS) classes to support the extended latency of the NT access and backhauling, as well as new radio access technologies allowing to discriminate the NT access.

NR protocols: NTN specific enhancing features

To support NTN, the NR system protocols have been enhanced with several fundamental features.

Some enhancements relate to the Physical Layer (PHY) of the protocol. These include the mitigation of the extended latency associated to NT networks in the timing relationship between uplink (UL) and downlink (DL). The Doppler shift/variation, as well as the large delay variation of LEO-based networks, have also to be addressed in the UL time and frequency synchronization. In NTN, the network broadcasts the ephemeris information and common Timing Advance (TA) parameter in each NTN cell (*i.e.*, the SIB-19 has been specified). Since in Rel. 17 the NTN-enabled UEs are equipped with Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) capabilities, they shall acquire a valid GNSS position, the satellite ephemeris, and the common TA (information received from the gNB) before connecting to an NTN cell.

To achieve UL synchronisation, before performing the Random Access (RA) procedure, the UE shall autonomously pre-compensate the TA and the frequency Doppler shift by considering its GNSS position, the common TA, the satellite position, and the satellite velocity (obtained through the SIB-19). In *connected mode*, the UE shall continuously update the TA and frequency pre-compensation values. In case a UE does not have valid GNSS and/or ephemeris information, it cannot communicate

with the network until both are regained. While the pre-compensation of the instantaneous Doppler shift on the service link is performed by the UE for the UL, it is worthwhile highlighting that its management on the feeder link is left to network implementation.

To mitigate the impact of Hybrid Automatic Repeat request (HARQ) stalling in NTN, the HARQ feedback can be disabled in the presence of ARQ re-transmissions at the Radio Link Control (RLC) layer (*e.g.*, in GSO satellite systems) and/or the number of HARQ processes for re-transmissions at the Medium Access Control (MAC) layer can be increased to 32 (*e.g.*, in NGSO satellite systems). On the UP, solutions to adjust the reception windows and to resolve the contention/preamble ambiguity for the Random Access (RA) procedure have been introduced.

In terms of mobility management, the NTN UE supports mobility between NTN and TN (*i.e.*, NTN-to-TN, and TN-to-NTN), but is not mandated to simultaneously connect to both the NTN and the TN. The mobility between radio access technologies based on different orbits (GSO/NGSO) can be supported.

Mobility enhancements in RRC_IDLE/RRC_INACTIVE and RRC_CONNECTED have been introduced: New measurement rules for cell re-selection with location information and timing information are introduced [TS 38.304]. Location assisted cell reselection is based on the distance between UE and the reference location of the cell (serving cell and/or neighbour cell). It is supported for quasi-earth fixed cell. The timing information is referring to the time when the serving cell is going to stop serving a geographical area. The timing and location information associated to a cell are provided via system information. For mobility enhancements in connected mode, a new measurement event (RRM Event D) based on location is introduced to trigger location reporting based on UE location. Further, triggering conditions upon which UE may execute Conditional Hand-Over (CHO) to a candidate cell, have been introduced: event A4 RRM measurement-based trigger, time-based trigger condition, location-based trigger condition. The two last conditions are configured together with one of the measurement-based trigger conditions. Location is defined by the distance between UE and a reference location (Event D1). Time is defined by the time between T1 and T2, where T1 is an absolute time value and T2 is a duration started at T1.

Handover procedures have been introduced on the feeder link, in particular for NGSO systems when the NTN payload shall change the serving GW due to its movement. The feeder link switch is a Transport Network layer procedure in which both hard and soft solutions are applicable.

The radio frequency (RF) performances of satellite payload have been defined on the service link for several exemplary bands, including L and S bands, based on adjacent channel co-existence studies between satellite and mobile networks captured in TR 38.863, [6]; this document provides the minimum RF and performance requirements in FR1 for the NR UEs supporting satellite access and the NR Satellite Access Node (SAN) are defined in TS 38.101-5, [7], and TS 38.108, [8]. The SAN is depicted in Figure 4, encompassing the on-ground non-NTN infrastructure gNB functions, the GW, the feeder link, and the RF functions of the NTN payload.

Figure 4. Satellite Access Node (SAN).

Table 3 summarises the operating bands and duplexing mode currently included in Rel. 17 NTN specifications. As per TS 38.101-5, an NTN-enabled UE must satisfy the same RF performance of a TN UE; this requirement allows a UE to connect to either the NTN or the legacy TN. In general, the RF

requirements for a SAN, defined in TS 38.108, are lower compared to those for terrestrial networks in TS 38.104, [9]. TS 38.133, [10], provides the requirements for Radio Resource Management (RRM) in NTN, in particular related to specific delay and timing/frequency errors in the different procedures.

Table 3. NTN operating bands and duplexing mode as per Rel. 17.

Satellite operating band	UL operating band (UE-to-SAN)	DL operating band (SAN-to-UE)	Duplexing mode
n256	1980 MHz – 2010 MHz	2170 MHz – 2200 MHz	FDD
n255	1626.5 MHz – 1660.5 MHz	1525 MHz – 1559 MHz	FDD

In addition to the SAN, the RF requirements were also defined for HAPS in TS 38.104; in this specification, the HAPS is described as a base station class referring to wide area base stations, without additional changes. These payloads can operate in NR band n1 (UL: 1920-1980 MHz, DL: 2110-2170 MHz) and the current NR UEs can support them without additional modifications.

Further details on the enhancements areas specified in 3GPP Rel.17 are shown in Figure 5.

RAN1: Physical layer <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timing relationship • UL time and frequency synchronization • Enhancements on HARQ • Polarization signaling for VSAT/ESIM 	RAN3: Access network architecture <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Identity handling • Registration Update and Paging Handling • Cell Relation Handling • Feeder Link Switch-Over (NGSO) • Aspects Related to Country-Specific Routing 	SA2: System level <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobility management with huge cell size • UE location and support of regulated service • QoS class for GEO satellite links • Impact of satellite backhauling
RAN2: Access layer <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User Plane: RACH aspects, Other MAC aspects (e.g. HARQ), UP: RLC, PDCP • System information broadcast • Control Plane: Tracking Area Management, Idle/connected mode mobility, UE Location Service 	RAN4: RF & RRM performance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New bands <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TN/NTN coexistence • Satellite Access Node, UE • RRM: e.g. timing compensation (idle, connected mode), GNSS accuracy 	CT1: Network protocols <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PLMN (re)selection • NAS timers

Figure 5. 3GPP NR-NTN specifications impact per TSG WG. Courtesy of: Mohamed El Jaafari, “3GPP NTN standardization: status and prospect,” ASMS/SPSC conference, September 2022.

NR NTN operating bands

With respect to the operating bands, these were summarised in Table 3. Figure 6 (see TR 38.863, [6]) provides an overview of the NR TN bands adjacent to the NTN n256 band. The NTN satellite band is adjacent to NR bands n1 (FDD) and n34 (TDD).

Figure 6. Adjacent TN bands to NTN band n256.

These bands need to be protected and co-existence analyses in adjacent bands are required to determine the Adjacent Channel Interference Ratio (ACIR) and in-band power levels, as showed in Figure 7 (for

scenarios resulted from coexistence with TN FDD n1 case) and Figure 8 (for additional scenarios resulted from coexistence with TN TDD n34 case).

Figure 7. S-band NTN-TN adjacent band coexistence scenarios with TN in FDD mode, [21].

In addition, NTN band n256 will be fully overlapped with TN NR band n65 and partially with TN NR bands n2, n25, n70, and n66, limiting band n256 deployments based on the countries where n2, n25 and/or, n70 are not deployed or regional regulation applies.

Figure 8. S-band NTN-TN adjacent band coexistence scenarios with TN in TDD mode (e.g., n34), [21].

As shown in Figure 9 (see TR 38.863, [6]), the NTN n255 band is not adjacent to any TN NR or LTE bands. The edge-to-edge separation for the nearest TN band, n74 DL, is 7 MHz. Then, NTN band n255 fully overlaps with TN NR band n24 and Supplementary UL (SUL) NR band n99. However, 3GPP work considers only coexistence with adjacent bands and MSS NTN S-band n256 core requirements resulted from coexistence simulations at 2 GHz have been reused also for MSS NTN L-band n255.

Figure 9. Adjacent TN bands to NTN band n255.

1.2 NTN features in Release 18 and 19

While the current NTN standardization framework already provides a solid ground for NTN integration in 5G, the definition of 5G-A NTN is already on-going within the recently started Rel. 18. Table 4 lists the current Study and Work Items; moreover, it also reports a recent SI dedicated to Rel. 19 NTN.

With respect to the recently started activities related to Rel. 18 NTN, the “NR_NTN_enh” WI aims at specifying further enhancements for the NG-RAN based NTN according to the following assumptions: i) GSO and NGSO systems; ii) Earth-fixed tracking area with Earth-fixed/moving cells for NGSO; iii) FDD mode; iv) UEs with GNSS capabilities; v) VSAT devices with directive antenna (including fixed and moving platform mounted devices) and commercial handheld terminals (*e.g.*, Power class 3) supported in FR1; and vi) only VSAT devices with directive antenna (including fixed and moving platform mounted devices) supported in FR2 (above 10 GHz). These assumptions include an implicit compatibility to support HAPS and Air-To-Ground (ATG) scenarios.

Table 4. NTN Study and Work Items in 3GPP Rel. 18 and Rel. 19.

Rel.	Item	Type	Lead WG	Title
18	5GSATB	WI	SA1	5G system with satellite backhaul
	FS_5GET	SI	SA1	Guidelines for Extra-territorial 5G Systems
	FS_5GSAT_Sec	SI	SA3	Study on Security Aspects of Satellite Access
	FS_NR_NTN_netw_verif_UE_loc	SI	RP	Study on requirements and use cases for network verified UE location for Non-Terrestrial-Networks (NTN) in NR
	FS_IoT_NTN	SI	SA5	Study on Management Aspects of IoT NTN Enhancements
	NR_NTN_enh	WI	RAN2	NR NTN (Non-Terrestrial Networks) enhancements
	IoT_NTN_enh	WI	RAN2	IoT (Internet of Things) NTN (non-terrestrial network) enhancements
	FS_5GSAT_Ph2	SI	SA2	Study on 5GC enhancement for satellite access Phase 2
	FS_5GSATB	SI	SA2	Study on Support of Satellite Backhauling in 5GS
19	FS_5GSAT_Ph3	SI	SA1	Study on satellite access - Phase 3

In this context, Table 5 lists all the features that will be defined by 3GPP as part of Rel. 18 for enhanced NTN systems according to the services: eMBB for NR and mMTC for 4G NB-IoT/eMTC.

Table 5. NTN features to be defined as part of 3GPP Rel. 18.

	eMBB (5G New Radio)	mMTC (4G NB-IoT, 4G eMTC)
SA2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Network based UE location determination Specifying system enhancements to support satellite discontinuous coverage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specifying system enhancements to support satellite discontinuous coverage
RAN WGs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coverage enhancements NR-NTN deployment in above 10 GHz bands and support for VSAT/ESIM NTN UE NTN-TN and NTN-NTN mobility and service continuity enhancements Network based UE location 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IoT-NTN Enhancements in Rel. 18 to address remaining issues from Rel. 17 Mobility enhancements Further enhancement to discontinuous coverage

Table 6. Potential NTN features to be defined as part of 3GPP Rel. 19.

Service	Performance enhancements	New capabilities
eMBB (5G NR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NTN-NTN or NTN-TN asynchronous Multi-Connectivity & Carrier Aggregation DL PAPR optimization Coordinated transmission 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regenerative payload (including edge computing) Support of MBS Relay-based architecture for NTN (for VSAT and ESIM)

Service	Performance enhancements	New capabilities
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Beam management and BWP association enhancements • Half Duplex FDD • Positioning enhancements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UE without GNSS • Intermittent/temporary satellite connectivity • NTN-TN Spectrum coexistence • Architecture for AI/ML 5G-NTN workflow to address specific SatCom issues
mMTC (4G NB-IoT/ eMTC)		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for store-and-forward on-board NTN payload • Location reporting by UEs • Architecture for AI/ML data-flow for the optimization of IoT-NTN systems • UE without GNSS

With respect to Rel. 19, preliminary studies have been carried out in Technical Specification Group Services and System Aspects. TR 22.865 captures the outcomes of the Study on satellite access - Phase 3 and it has been drafted in August 2022. The objectives of this SI are to analyse new use cases and aspects related to enhancements of the 5G system over satellite, including:

- support operations with intermittent/temporary satellite connectivity (*e.g.*, in NGSO systems) for delay-tolerant communication services (*e.g.*, to provide communication services for UEs under satellite coverage without a simultaneous active feeder link connection to the ground segment);
- support also UEs without GNSS capabilities;
- positioning enhancements, in particular by performing a gap analysis between the existing positioning requirements in TNs and those that can be satisfied via NTN, determining the potential updates to NTN positioning Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and study new relevant regulatory requirements (if any);
- communication between UEs under the same satellite's coverage, in particular analysing the potential additional service requirements, *e.g.*, in terms of latency.

Table 6 lists the above features and an educated guess on other potential performance enhancements and new capabilities that will be addressed within Rel. 19.

1.3 6G NTN system vision

In the above context, while the interest and effort in the framework of 3GPP NTN has been continuously increasing, it is clear that enhancements will enable increased performance and/or new capabilities for the NTN component in 5G-A and future 6G systems. The definition of 6G networks and requirements is at its very infancy, with ITU-R WP 5D that recently initiated the development of a document reporting the IMT vision for 2030 and beyond, [12]-[13]; this study also rely on the outcome of the ITU-T Focus Group Technologies for Network 2030 (FG-NET-2030), which between 2018 and 2020 defined a set of preliminary target services for 6G.

Initial speculations on the main 6G use cases highlight that Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), digital twinning, and immersive communications (*e.g.*, tactile/haptic Internet) will be among the major vertical drivers, [12]-[14]. With 6G and beyond, it is expected to create a fully connected world, where the physical world is represented in high detail in the digital domain, in which it can be analysed and also acted upon. The network would provide links between the domains by devices embedded everywhere, as well as provide the infrastructure and the intelligence of the digital domain. Humans will be placed in the middle of this cyber-physical continuum, with both bodies and intelligence connected. This means that 6G will have to achieve many more objectives than just providing extremely fast mobile connectivity. Some considerations can be as follows:

- the convergence of the physical, human, and digital worlds in 6G will require support for digital twinning, immersive communication, cognition, and connected intelligence;
- the provision of flexibility and programmability should be at the heart of 6G;
- 6G shall support deterministic end-to-end services;
- 6G shall provide integrated sensing and communication, which will enable high-accuracy localization and high-resolution sensing services;
- 6G will play an ambitious role towards sustainability, to reduce its footprint on energy, resources, and emissions and to improve sustainability in other parts of society and industry;
- 6G needs to become a truly trustworthy infrastructure that will become the basis of the societies of the future;
- 6G must be scalable and affordable, to ensure that it can be inclusive for all people across the world;
- 6G needs, where required, to significantly stretch the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that 5G can achieve today.

6G systems will be studied in 3GPP as part of Rel. 20 and then start to be defined in Rel. 21.

As previously mentioned, the preliminary set of KPIs targeted for 6G are being discussed in research projects feeding the IMT Future Technology Trends Towards 2030 and Beyond. Among the various trends, it is worth to highlight the following:

- throughput/data rate up to 1 Tbit/s;
- user-experienced data rate of 1 Gbit/s (ten times the one targeted by 5G);
- end-to-end latency less than 1 ms;
- over-the-air latency of 10–100 μ s with mobility up to 1000 km/h;
- very broad bandwidth, with frequencies reaching 1–3 THz;
- "always-ON" terrestrial-aerial-satellite network;
- Frame Error Rate (FER), *i.e.*, reliability, equal to $1-10^{-9}$;
- very high energy efficiency also supporting "battery-free IoT devices" (10-100 times the one of 5G) and especially equal to 1 pJ/bit;
- spectrum efficiency greater than three times the one of 5G;
- receiver sensitivity less than -130 dBm;
- connectivity density ten times the one provided by 5G, with an area traffic capacity of up to 1 Gbit/s/m²;
- density of connected devices greater than 10⁶/km²;
- 1 cm localisation precision in three dimensions.

In order to cope with such demanding and challenging requirements, it is widely recognised that the unification of the terrestrial and non-terrestrial infrastructure components will be fundamental. In fact, as shown in 10, before 5G, TN and NTN were independently optimised; then, with 5G and 5G-A, the objective has been the optimisation of the TN and integration of the NTN component with minimum impact. However, only with 6G systems TN and NTN will be jointly optimised in a unified and fully integrated multi-layered infrastructure. Such architecture will combine terrestrial, airborne, and spaceborne radio access networks for the envisaged

Figure 10. Interaction between TN and NTN before, during, and beyond 5G.

convergence of the physical, human, and digital worlds. With this approach, there is a great opportunity to optimize the 6G service performances (throughput and service rate) over the satellite component taking into account its specific characteristics and operational constraints.

Moreover, thanks to a native support of multi connectivity and mobility across access technologies based on space assets at different orbit together with terrestrial access technologies, the Quality of Experience (QoE), the service reliability are expected to be greatly improved.

6G NTN is clearly an unexplored area within 3GPP, as it will be addressed from Rel. 20. However, in the following sections, we will discuss our view on the use cases, architectures, and technologies for 6G, evolving from those defined in 5G (Rel. 15-Rel. 17) and in the on-going Rel. 18/19 (5G-A).

2 USE CASE EVOLUTION AND PERFORMANCE REQUIREMENTS

2.1 5G NTN use cases

A set of use cases for 5G NTN was initially identified in 3GPP TR 22.822, [15]. In this technical report, it is reported that NTN can bring an added value to complement the terrestrial RAN in terms of:

- Service **continuity**: terrestrial networks are typically deployed based on the users' density. This approach led to the Digital Divide problem, in which many geographical areas have limited or no broadband access via terrestrial communications. In this context, NTN can be a viable solution to provide connectivity for pedestrian/fixed UEs, or moving platforms (train, aircraft, maritime), which cannot be served by a single or a combination of terrestrial networks.
- Service **ubiquity**: in addition to economic motivations leading to Digital Divide areas, terrestrial networks might also be temporarily or geographically unavailable due to natural disasters or terrorist attacks, partially or completely disrupting the communication infrastructure. In this context, NTN are again a viable solution to ensure both consumer service provisioning and a working communication infrastructure for the first responders on the area.
- Service **scalability**: notably, NTN elements cover much larger areas compared to terrestrial cells. This unique feature makes satellites, HAPS, and drones extremely efficient in providing broadcasting and multicasting services. Moreover, NTN systems can also off-load the traffic of the terrestrial networks during peak hours.

The definition of new satellite-based use cases has been addressed also within ITU-R, which published a report about vision, the requirements and evaluation guidelines for the satellite component of IMT-2020. Inspired by terrestrial NR, three categories are considered: i) enhanced Mobile Broadband via satellite (eMBB-s); ii) massive Machine Type Communications via satellite (mMTC-s); and iii) High Reliability Communications via satellite (HRC-s).

Based on both 3GPP and ITU-R discussions, Figure 11 depicts the envisioned potential use cases for 5G NTN, in which the main characteristics for each scenario, discussed below, are highlighted.

Figure 11. 5G NTN use cases based on ITU-R IMT-2020 vision for satellite systems.

2.1.1 enhanced Mobile Broadband via satellite (eMBB-s)

This category will essentially consist of eMBB services for mass-market consumers, typically leisure services (*e.g.*, for vehicular networks in maritime domain), and connectivity for enterprises. Satellite broadband services aims to complement 5G terrestrial services, typically in unserved and underserved areas, since a major asset of satellites is global coverage enabling ubiquitous services.

Future broadband services are seen as having significantly more capacity and higher user data rates than today's capabilities, so as to meet the growing demands of users. The main objectives consist in providing increased data-rate, resilience, continuity, and much higher resource efficiency including a

significant decrease in energy consumption. The technologies addressing broadband services will be reused to address governmental services with some additional features, essentially security, [16].

eMBB-s represent the natural evolution for the current and massive usages of 4G for Internet and broadband access in general, as we know today. Logically, eMBB is therefore a priority over the other categories due to shorter time-to-market targets. This has an incidence on the standardization process. It shall be reminded that eMBB is not restricted to services towards mobile handsets. Indeed, a variety of new usages, in particular for fixed terminals (access to *4G Boxes*, industrial devices using cellular access requiring some connectivity services, etc.). The topic of convergence between wireline and wireless convergence is addressed in a dedicated 3GPP study for Rel. 16, [17].

Last, it shall also be noted that 5G ambitions to address system level converge with fixed access services (the so called Fixed / Mobile Convergence), justified by the dual role of Mobile Network Operators (MNO) and fixed telcos providers. Benefits clearly appear to make infrastructures and technologies common and fully shared.

2.1.2 massive Machine Type Communications via satellite (mMTC-s)

Many potential services can be provided in the context of IoT by exploiting a satellite RAN. Since they all share many aspects related to the infrastructure and the interaction with a terrestrial network, they are all categorized at high level as an IoT (or mMTC) via satellite framework.

Global NB-IoT/mMTC coverage

The objective is to guarantee a continuous global coverage of NB-IoT/mMTC devices for any type of data transfer between the terminals and a central server, as long as non-delay critical communications are involved. This can be achieved by means of a (mega-)constellation of LEO satellites. The IoT terminals can be on moving platforms, *e.g.*, vehicles, and, thus, can also experience the lack of a terrestrial infrastructure guaranteeing connectivity. In order to allow the IoT service provider to not interrupt its service, the satellite network can either directly provide the IoT service to the terminals in its coverage area or complement the terrestrial network(s) in un-/under-served areas by means of roaming agreements with the satellite network operator. In this scenario, the 5G system shall be able to select the optimal access network to provide the required service, when both terrestrial and satellite access is possible.

Smart good tracking

A moving platform (ship, train, or cargo flight) or a truck might be carrying goods which must be continuously monitored and localized (*e.g.*, COVID-19 vaccines). To this aim, it is required that the boxes or containers are equipped with sensors that provide: i) the location, as a mandatory parameter; and ii) an optional set of parameters that allow to remotely keep track of the status of the good (*e.g.*, the temperature of the boxes in which COVID-19 vaccines are being transported). A terrestrial network cannot guarantee the continuous coverage in any area and, thus, the possibility to rely on satellite access through one or more Satellite Network Operators (SNO) would actually be fundamental. For instance: i) a cargo flight can be connected to the terrestrial infrastructure while parked or taxiing, but it needs satellite access during the flight; ii) trains or vehicles are likely to pass through scarcely populated areas with no terrestrial infrastructures, thus requiring an NTN solution; or iii) a ship can be connected to a terrestrial infrastructure when anchored or navigating close to the land, but in off-shore areas it must rely on satellite access. It is worthwhile mentioning that, in order to monitor the goods being transported, there are two options: i) each box is equipped with a UE which directly connects to the MNO/SNO; or ii) each box is equipped with only sensors that report their status to an aggregation point (*e.g.*, an Integrated Access and Backhaul, IAB, node), which then communicates, with larger capacity, all of the data to the MNO/SNO, [18].

2.1.3 High Reliability Communications via satellite (HRC-s)

This service category poses specific requirements and challenges related to availability and reliability. Among the various applications, we describe those deemed the most relevant.

Governmental services

Governmental services mainly address services under the responsibility of governmental organisations (ministers, health organisations, security organisations, transports organisations, etc.) for various purposes (*e.g.*, secure communications between entities, border and event surveillances, traffic management, search, and rescue, etc.). The final user can be specific members of an organisation or any singular customer.

Emergency management

This service refers to scenarios in which a natural disaster or a terrorist attack destroy, fully or partially, part of the RAN, which thus becomes unavailable. Consequently, all of the services provided by one or more MNOs operating through the disrupted terrestrial infrastructure cannot be guaranteed anymore. The restoration of the communication infrastructure on the area is fundamental for both the population and, in particular, the first responders that need a telecommunication infrastructure to coordinate their efforts and to report to the command center the evolution of the rescue operations.

In this scenario, LEO satellites, HAPS, or drones can provide coverage with a sufficiently low latency. It is worth mentioning that the capacity requests in such scenario can range from very low values (*e.g.*, simply reporting the locations of the different rescue teams to the command center, which can be in the same area or remote) to quite large (*e.g.*, Augmented Reality, AR, helmets provided to the first responders, sending their videos to the command center).

Ground-based infrastructures are vulnerable to natural disasters: floods, earthquakes, hurricanes, and fires may not only devastate a territory, but also destroy the ground infrastructure of its communication network, increasing the difficulties relief personnel may encounter. At the moment, satellite communications may be provided by using civilian satellites and satellite-specific ground terminals, both handheld and fixed, but those may not always be available. Additionally, those terminals are often bulky and unavailable to non-relief personnel. A possible development with regards to this use case could use a deployable support drones to cover a large area and offer a backhauling service for end users: contrary to current satellite networks, handheld terminals should be able to interface and access directly to the drones, allowing a larger number of users to access the network.

The drones would act as access points to the network, in the vest of relays for the end users on ground towards the LEO satellites. From there an ISL network could transmit the data to the various core network GWs. Such network would be temporary, and can benefit from Software Defined Network (SDN) capabilities to optimize coverage and resource allocation, as well as, where possible and necessary, active antennas, beamforming and other techniques to improve and optimize the service.

The time constraints of emergency coverage as well as the mandatory global coverage require a LEO constellation composed of a large number of satellites. The number of satellites depends mostly on the altitude and it shall be defined once the acceptable delay has been computed. This layer should act as the core network of the system, relaying data from satellites in visibility to the ground stations through ISL. Also this portion of the network should include Software Defined Radio (SDR) capabilities in order to be able to re-route data traffic efficiently towards the closest ground gateway. MEO and GEO networks would require a minor number of satellites, but for emergency services, where real-time communication is mandatory, such an approach may prove unfeasible because of the noticeably increased latency.

In general, the requirements for this service category can be the following:

- the 5G/5G-A system shall guarantee the connectivity through the satellite component when the terrestrial network is not available;

- mission-critical communications shall be given priority over other services. Then, in case enough capacity can be provided, part of it can be allocated to routing baseline services (*e.g.*, SMS, voice, limited data traffic) to the users;
- in case AR connectivity shall be provided, Multi-Connectivity or other advanced techniques (*e.g.*, Cell-Free MIMO, CF-MIMO). In this case, the UEs shall support such techniques.

For handheld terminals, such as smartphones and tablets, more specific terminals will be required for connecting and piloting drones. The main motivation behind this scenario is to guarantee the continuity of the service to users on the ground in the event of a disaster or unavailability of the ground service; hence, drones should be fully compatible with the average handheld terminal. Any deployable ground terminals can support connectivity or act as relay stations.

Remote control/monitoring of critical infrastructures

In this case, the 5G system aims at remotely controlling and monitoring critical infrastructures, as, *e.g.*, an off-shore wind farm. In general, independently from the specific application, the following traffic flows can be foreseen: i) remote monitoring and non-time-critical control of operations, with moderate capacity requirements and low latency (thus requiring HAPS or LEO); ii) continuous data upload for data analytics, characterised by large capacity requirements and no restriction on the latency; iii) on-demand download of sensor data for remote analysis, which might involve large capacities and no restriction on latency; iv) video surveillance during on-demand maintenance, with High Definition (HD) video transmission (large capacity) and low latency requirements; and v) on-demand provision of information from the remote control center to on-site personnel, which might involve large capacity but no time criticality. To this aim, the 5G system shall support potentially large uplink/downlink data rates via satellite, guarantee a large service availability and reliability, and guarantee a high level of reconfigurability so as to tailor the communication parameters to the different latency and capacity requirements.

2.2 NTN use case evolution²

2.2.1 5G-Advanced

Currently, within 3GPP it is not foreseen to introduce novel use cases or services for NTN-based 5G-A systems (*i.e.*, in the framework of Rel. 18 and Rel. 19). Clearly, it can be expected that the evolution in terms of technologies, architectures, and techniques, described in the other sections of this document, will positively impact the performance of the above discussed 5G services in the context of 5G-A. However, it is worthwhile highlighting that, since Rel. 14, 3GPP introduced features to enable MNOs to directly provide television services over standardised interfaces. In the context of Multicast and Broadcast Services (MBS), in which an ever increasing capacity request is being experienced (*e.g.*, due to the increase in the number of Ultra-High Definition (UHD) programs in broadcasting services), satellite networks provide an efficient access option to:

- serve users located in un-served areas;
- serve users with the required QoS when the MNO is saturating due to the large traffic requests, *i.e.*, for traffic off-loading.

The satellite overlay can address not only the distribution of video content, but any type of digital content to be provided to several UEs distributed over a large geographical area. In this case, the following scenarios can be envisaged:

- the UE is indoor and, thus, it can only be served by means of an MNO. However, NTN can be exploited as a backhaul solution;

² Please note that the 6G NTN use cases are under definition and those reported in this Section refer to the unified TN-NTN 6G network.

- the UE is outdoor in the coverage area of both the MNO and a SNO. In this case, advanced techniques can be exploited to significantly enhance the capacity, *e.g.*, MC. Another opportunity for this scenario is to off-load the traffic from the terrestrial to the satellite network;
- the UE is outdoor and in the coverage of the SNO only, thus requiring direct connectivity to the NTN elements.

In general, this use case requires that: i) the 5G/5G-A system can support both terrestrial and satellite access; ii) the 5G/5G-A system should implement procedures and techniques to optimally distribute the content (in particular when both MNOs and SNOs are available); and iii) the UE should be able to connect to both terrestrial and non-terrestrial infrastructures (with the additional possibility to manage parallel bearers from such nodes), [18].

2.2.2 6G

6G will enable diverse use cases with extreme range of requirements. Compared to legacy design requirements, the biggest difference is the diversity of use-cases that 6G networks must support and the new opportunities it will create compared to today's networks. These use cases can be grouped into the following six usage scenarios for 6G that are being discussed in the industry, extending and expanding those of 5G:

- Ultra-Mobile Broadband;
- Immersive Communication;
- Ultra-Critical Communications;
- Ubiquitous MTC and Ultra massive connectivity;
- Network Sensing;
- Artificial Intelligence.

Figure 12. Service evolution from 5G, to 5G-Advanced, to 6G.

These six usage scenarios are illustrated in Figure 12, which summarises the evolution from 5G, to 5G-Advanced and, finally, to 6G NTN systems.

Ultra MBB and Immersive Communication

Ultra Mobile Broadband is about massive broadband that delivers gigabytes of bandwidth on demand and more importantly improving the consistency of end-user experience, data rate of user wherever she/he is located is constant.

The demand for mobile broadband will continue to increase, leading to ultra-Mobile Broadband. Naturally 6G will have to support mobile broadband connections as of today with increased capacity,

efficiency and data transmission rates. Ultra Mobile Broadband addresses the human-centric use cases for access to multi-media content, services and data.

The Ultra Mobile Broadband usage scenario will come with new application areas and requirements in addition to existing Mobile Broadband applications for improved performance and an increasingly seamless user experience. Typical use cases corresponding to Ultra MBB include but not limited to Holographic Communications, immersive AR/VR and telepresence.

Holography is a method of producing a 3D image of a physical object by recording, on a light-sensitive medium (*e.g.*, photographic plate), the pattern of interference formed by a split laser beam where one of the beam paths interacts with the 3D object in question. The resulting interference pattern contains the complete optical amplitude (intensity), phase (depth) and wavelength (colour) information that characterize a visual representation of any 3D object formed by the human brain. When the interference pattern is illuminated either with a laser or with ordinary light, the optical amplitude and phase information of the original object is regenerated, and the human brain perceives a realistic 3D picture of the original object.

Studies based on human perception of 2D images and conventional 3D videos that use binocular parallax technology to create 3D effect and holograms reveal that a holographic display comes closest to satisfying all visual cues for human visual observation of any 3D object. In other words, for humans, true holograms are the best substitutes for natural sight.

In the next decade, network advancements are expected to enable fully immersive user experiences virtually. A key component of the immersive nature of user experience is the transmission of 3D holographic images from one/multiple sources to one/multiple endpoints in an interactive manner. There are a variety of user-device oriented technologies, such as AR/VR via head-mounted display (HMD) devices. However, fully immersive, and interactive 3D holographic imaging/streaming will be a challenge even for future networks.

Ultra-Critical Communications and Ubiquitous MTC

Ultra-Critical Communications applies to use cases with stringent latency, reliability and availability requirements. The automotive industries in general have tremendous interests for integration of those services in 6G for the Vehicular-to-Everything (V2X) services.

The typical use cases include Tactile/Haptic and Digital Twin.

The Tactile Internet can be considered as the next evolution of IoT. The Tactile Internet encompasses human-to-machine and machine-to-machine interaction enabling a variety of real-time interactive and control systems applicable to industrial, societal, and business use cases. It adds a new dimension to human-to-machine interaction by enabling transmission of human touch and haptic sensations. This enables humans and machines to interact with their environment, while on the move and within a certain physical range over which communication takes place. The Tactile Internet may also revolutionize machine to machine interactions by building upon the next industrial revolution, Industry 4.0, with the addition of human interactions into the mix. If developed properly, the promise of this combination will be nothing short of revolutionary for how humans learn and work using the Internet.

Robotic surgery is one example of the Tactile Internet. At one end is the human system interface, which is a master console where the surgeon gets a real-time audio-visual-haptic feed of the patient and operating room. Additional data feeds such as patient diagnostics and reactions are provided in real time. The visual feed is provided using real-time holographic streaming technology with adjustments based on whether the surgeon is wearing a head mounted display device or interacting with a hologram. As the surgeon proceeds with the operation the haptic-enabled robots (Human System Interface) at the patient-end mimics the surgeon's actions with high reliability, fidelity, and minimum latency. Real-time feedback (audio/ visual/haptic/patient diagnostic) from the patient side is transmitted back to the surgeon throughout the surgery process.

Another example is remote industrial management that involves remote real-time monitoring and control of industrial machinery. Remote control is enabled using tactile sensors providing kinaesthetic

feedback from the machine to the operator. Tactile feedback is augmented real-time audio-visual information, possibly using holography/VR technologies. To complete the closed-loop control, as with the surgery example above, diagnostic information (in this case from the machine/tool under remote operation control) is also fed back to the operator in real time.

The Tactile Internet use cases generally comprise real-time interactions that require the network to have very low end-to-end latency and guaranteed high bandwidth support. True interactive control in the Tactile Internet requires stringent synchronization between various data feeds, [19].

A Digital Twin is a virtualization model of a physical process, product, or service all accomplished by using simulations in the digital domain.

Digital Twin technology can be applied to various scenarios. An example use case is advanced manufacturing. The ultimate goal is to create, test, and build equipment in a virtual environment and only when that equipment performs to exact specifications (in the virtual environment) will physical manufacturing be allowed to start. Once manufactured, the physical build would be linked to its Digital Twin through sensors so that the Digital Twin contains all the information that its physical counterpart possesses.

Another notable use case scenario for Digital Twin technology is Smart City planning. A modern city is a dynamic complex system composed of people, processes, services, events, infrastructure, etc. Using a Digital Twin model of the real city makes Digital Twin a powerful tool for operation, planning and evolution of future smart cities.

The underlying networking requirements for enabling Digital Twins include bandwidth, latency, elasticity etc.

Mobile networks are also becoming part of a critical national security strategy where governments see a need for advanced communication technologies and ubiquitous connectivity to operate with speed, precision, and efficiency.

Governments want to deploy their national security enterprise networks more quickly and with lower cost. Governments see the possibility of efficiency gains, rapid deployment, and adaptation of their facility operations with automated vehicles and logistics with future networks ready to deploy anywhere, anytime.

National security requirements for future networks call for ubiquitous high-speed connectivity for moving massive amounts of data in dense networks and for low-latency communications to enable new generations of unmanned and autonomous systems, both in the air and on the ground.

Effective and survivable future networks must operate in contested environments with constant threats and counter with new capabilities. Spectrum sensing systems will classify signals to detect denial-of-service attacks and self-organizing radio access networks will dynamically use the spectrum to continue operations unimpeded. Future networks must counter attacks on data traffic and control elements with national security-specific enhancements not found in commercial networks today, including robust network protocols and air interfaces with low-probability of intercept and detection.

In NTN, low latency use cases can be considered, taking into account the possibilities of ISLs, but taking in consideration the rerouting and processing delays, such an architecture cannot be used for remote control or navigation.

In this case as well, an autonomous rerouting capability would be necessary: SDR and shared resources to optimize the connectivity between HAPS and LEO/GEO depending on the typology of services would be fundamental, allowing the network to act similarly as a ground-based network, with access nodes and smart rerouting of information depending on the requested latency and QoS.

Network sensing and Artificial Intelligence

The integration of communication and sensing is expected to play a decisive role in realizing the vision of a 6G 3D network as also detailed in the following section, [20]. Sensing-assisted communications allows to utilize 6G wireless communication systems more effectively and realize wide area multi-dimensional sensing. It will provide beyond-communication spatial-temporal services such as an increased environmental awareness, imaging, mapping, advanced localization, tracking and posture/gesture recognition.

Particularly, in a 6G NTN network sensing-assisted communications will enhance Radio Resource Management (RRM) efficiency, *e.g.*, to optimize radio resource utilization considering user movement trajectory and environmental changes, improve beam management algorithm, enhance spectrum utilization and enhance network energy performance.

AI/ML is impacting every aspect of business and society. AI will also shape how future communication networks will evolve. Many of the potential 6G use cases assume AI/ML services, enabled through a distributed edge architecture with integrated communication and computing capabilities, agnostic to licenced or unlicensed spectrum. Typical AI/ML applications include training and inference for image recognition, creation and prediction with digital twins, collaborative robots/cobots for complicated tasks, improve autonomy of each device and universal support connection/operation, as well as intelligent interaction to quickly transfer knowledge and accumulate skills for human and machines, etc., [19].

2.3 Target performance

With respect to the target performance, different service requirements for different deployment contexts and terminal types shall be defined. In particular, the following use cases are deemed to be the most relevant for future 5G-A and 6G NTN systems:

- 5G-Advanced: i) handheld outdoor terminals, for pedestrian users and Public Safety services; and ii) VSAT on mobile platforms or building mounted.
- 6G: i) handheld terminals, outdoor or in light indoor conditions; and ii) vehicle or drone mounted terminals.

Table 7 reports the target performance for the above mentioned deployment scenarios.

Table 7: Target performance requirements for 5G-Advanced and 6G services.

Terminal and deployment		Experienced data rate (DL/UL) [Mbps]	Latency [ms]		Reliability	Position error [m]	Position acquisition time [s]	UE speed [km/h]	Connection density [UE/km ²]
			UP	CP					
5G-A	Handheld, outdoor	1/0.1	GEO <600 MEO <180 LEO <50	<40	99.99%	<1	<2	3 (pedestrian)	[100]
	Handheld, outdoor Public Safety	5/5			99.999%	<1	<1	100	[50]
	Mobile platforms and building mounted VSATs	50/25			99.99%	<1	<2	<250	[100]
6G	Handheld, light indoor	1/0.1 (at least emergency services)			99.999%	<0.1	<1	N/A	[100]
	Handheld, outdoor	20/2			99.999%	<0.1	<1	3 (pedestrian)	[50]
	Vehicle or drone mounted	80/40 (<6 GHz) 300/150 (>6 GHz)			99.999%	<0.1	<1	100	[100]

It shall be highlighted that for connection density the values are in square brackets, meaning that they shall not yet be considered as a specific target performance. In fact, depending on the beam size and the target coverage area, the number of UEs that shall be served by the NTN system might be excessive for current and near-future payloads. Thus, the connection density shall be rather considered as a parameter to be assessed and evaluated to actually understand the limits of the overall system in terms of connected terminals.

With respect to the deployment scenarios involving mobile platforms, it is worthwhile highlighting that, as part of 5G-Advanced, the objective is to enhance NTN so that platform-mounted relays (IAB nodes) can be deployed. This will allow to embark an access point on board the transportation platforms, such as trains, ships, and airplanes, that can be connected through the 5G NTN access network. In 6G, the specific installation constraints of car-/drone-mounted installations, such as the volume, shape, and energy efficiency, shall be taken into account when designing the NTN connectivity. Thus, this deployment scenario is considered for 6G systems.

3 NTN SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE EVOLUTION

The NTN system architecture in 5G-NR systems is based on transparent payloads and operations in FR1, *i.e.*, below 6 GHz (see Section 1 for information on the normative work). In order to cope with the challenging requirements and users' demands for 5G-Advanced and 6G systems, an innovation breakthrough is needed in terms of the architecture as well. As represented in Figure 13, such evolution will encompass the inclusion of three additional solutions for 5G-A: i) regenerative payloads; ii) Multi-Connectivity (MC); and iii) indirect access through Integrated Access and Backhaul (IAB) nodes. Then, a further leap will be needed to move to 6G communications and realise a truly unified terrestrial-satellite communication infrastructure that we envision as a three-dimensional Multi-Layer Multi-Orbit Multi-Band (3D ML-MO-MB) NTN.

Figure 13. NTN architecture evolution from 5G to 5G-Advanced and 6G.

3.1 5G NTN: transparent payload

In the first NTN specifications, the focus is on transparent payload architectures with direct access to the UEs, as shown in Figure 3 and reported, for the sake of clarity, in Figure 14. The transparent payload implements only frequency conversion, filtering, and amplification, and the gNB serving the on-ground UEs is conceptually located at the GW. Consequently, aiming at the full compatibility with the 3GPP NR standard, both the feeder and the user service links shall be implemented by means of the NR-Uu Air Interface. In fact, a satellite equipped with a transparent payload can neither terminate the NR-Uu procedures nor manage the QoS flows. Based on these observations, the NG-RAN contains the gNB, the NTN GW, and the NTN payload.

Figure 14. NTN architecture with transparent payload and direct access.

It is worthwhile highlighting that the architecture in Figure 14 only shows a single gNB. However, each gNB is capable of managing a few tens of beams, while in multi-beam NTN systems each satellite might be generating even hundreds of beams, depending on the mission requirements. Thus, in order to manage the NTN node, multiple gNBs might be needed. In case the satellites generate a reduced number of beams, then a single gNB can serve multiple payloads.

Since the NR-Uu Air Interface implemented on the service and feeder links was specifically designed for terrestrial systems, it is of paramount importance to assess the impact of the NTN channel impairments on the various radio protocol layers. These analyses are reported in 3GPP TR 38.811 and TR 38.821, as detailed in the normative overview provided in Section 1.

In terms of functional split, since this architecture is based on a transparent payload, the on-ground gNB implements both the CU and the DU. Referring to Figure 15, reporting the different functional split options for NR, option 8 is considered for 5G. It enables the complete separation of the RF from the PHY. Everything from the PHY and above is centralized, leading to a very tightly coordinated RAN. This allows an efficient support of the 5G features that require extremely low latency, like high order MIMO or high diversity for Ultra Reliable and Low Latency Communications (URLLC) traffic, as long

as the end-to-end connectivity to the core network is considered. Clearly, when considering the gNB-UE path only, lower latencies can be achieved by means of regenerative payloads.

Figure 15. Radio Access Network (RAN) Split Options.

3.2 5G-Advanced NTN

As mentioned above, the evolution from 5G to 5G-A NTN architectures is moving along three directions: i) the inclusion of regenerative payloads; ii) the implementation of Multi-Connectivity solutions; and iii) the exploitation of indirect access through IAB nodes.

3.2.1 Regenerative payloads

For regenerative payloads, radio frequency filtering, frequency conversion and amplification as well as demodulation/decoding, switch and/or routing, coding/modulation are implemented on-board. This is effectively equivalent to having all or part of the gNB protocol stack on the NTN platform. The exploitation of regenerative payloads allows, among the others, to implement various functional split options and Inter-Satellite Links, which might operate in RF or optical frequency bands.

Depending on the selected functional split options, different operations will be performed on-ground (gNB-CU) and on-board (gNB-DU), as detailed below.

Full gNB on-board

Figure 16 shows the architecture with a regenerative payload and the entire gNB implemented on-board. In this case, the NR-Uu protocols are entirely terminated on-board, *i.e.*, this Air Interface is only present on the user service link. Consequently, the GW basically acts as a Transport

Figure 16. NTN architecture with regenerative payload and direct access, full gNB on-board.

Network layer node, terminating all transport protocols and connecting to the 5G Core network (5GC) and the on-board gNB via the NG interface. This Air Interface is logical, *i.e.*, it can be implemented by means of any Satellite Radio Interface (SRI), as, for instance, the DVB-S2, DVB-S2X, or DVB-RCS2.

This architecture option allows to significantly reduce the over-the-air latency, since all NR-Uu protocols are dealt with by the regenerative payload on-board; however, it is also more complex and the cost of the satellite, and, thus, of the overall NTN system, is increased.

gNB-DU on-board

Figure 17 shows the architecture options with a regenerative payload and only the gNB-CU on-board. On the one hand, this allows a scalable solution based on Network Function Virtualisation (NFV) and Software Defined Networks (SDN) concepts, so as to tailor the system to different use cases and vertical services, in addition to an overall improved performance in terms of network management. On the other hand, the overall system cost and complexity are (even significantly) increased.

As discussed in 3GPP TS 38.401, [24], it shall be mentioned that: i) a gNB can be split into a gNB-CU and one or more gNB-DUs; ii) each gNB-DU can be connected to a single gNB-CU, while a single gNB-CU can manage multiple gNB-DUs; and iii) the gNB-CU and the gNB-DU(s) are connected through the F1 and E1 Air Interfaces for the UP and CP, respectively. These interfaces are again logical and, thus, can be implemented by means of any SRI as long as specific signalling operations are guaranteed. This architecture poses a challenge related to the F1 interface since it requires a *persistent connection* between the gNB-DU and the gNB-CU and it cannot be closed and re-activated on-demand; as such, with moving satellites as in a NGSO non-stationary scenario, all of the connections towards the served UEs would be dropped once the satellite is outside of the visibility of the current gNB-CU. Smart implementations of the F1 interface and/or the functional split in NTN shall thus be designed.

Figure 17. NTN architecture with regenerative payload and direct access, gNB-CU on-board.

As also shown in Figure 15, there are several options for being able to split functionality and each is optimized for specific use cases. Currently, those considered as the most relevant are option 2 (RRC/PDCP split), Option 6 (MAC/PHY split), and Option 7 (Low PHY/High PHY split). However, it is worthwhile highlighting that only Option 2 is fully supported by 3GPP, which includes the F1/E1 interfaces; the other options are clearly possible, but they are not yet 3GPP-compliant up to Rel. 17 and they shall be implemented by means of O-RAN or Common Public Radio Interface (CPRI) solutions.

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3.2.2 Integrated Access and Backhaul

In relay-based access solution, the UEs do not directly connect to the gNB, but to an Integrated Access and Backhaul (IAB) node. This network element was introduced in Rel. 16 as a flexible solution for multi-hop backhauling and to address dense deployment scenarios, minimising the impact on the core network; the IAB architecture is scalable and the only limitation to the number of hops is given by the network performance. Currently, indirect access solutions based on IAB are considered for further study within 3GPP; and as such can be considered for 5G-A. As detailed in TR 38.809, [25], and TR 38.874, [26], an IAB-Donor acts as gNB and it is connected to the 5GC through NG Air Interface. It includes the CP/UP of the IAB-Donor gNB-CU and then one or more IAB DUs which manage other IABs in a hierarchical architecture. Each IAB DU: i) is connected to one or more IAB-nodes, in particular to their Mobile Termination (MT), through the F1 logical interface on the CP and the NR-Uu interface on the UP; and/or ii) is connected to the UEs to be served via the NR-Uu Air Interface. It is also worthwhile mentioning that the IAB-Donor implements PDCP/SDAP and upper layers, while the IAB-nodes only implement the PHY, MAC, and RLC layers, *i.e.*, the functional split corresponds to option 2.

Figure 18 shows the architecture with a transparent payload and indirect access to the UEs. The IAB-Donor is connected to the 5GC via the NG interface, as previously mentioned; the connection between the IAB-Donor and the IAB-node(s), *i.e.*, both the user access and feeder links, is implemented by means of the NR-Uu (UP) and logical F1 (CP) Air Interfaces.

Figure 18. NTN architecture with transparent payload and IAB-based access.

Figure 19 shows the architecture with IAB-access when the IAB-Donor is on-ground and the IAB-node is on-board. In this case, the same Air Interfaces as those discussed above for the transparent payload case shall be implemented.

Figure 19. NTN architecture with regenerative payload and IAB-based access, on-ground IAB-Donor.

Figure 20 shows the case with an on-board IAB-Donor. Here, the feeder link connecting the IAB-Donor to the 5GC via the system GW shall be implemented as a NG-SRI interface.

Figure 20. NTN architecture with regenerative payload and IAB-based access, on-board IAB-Donor.

In terms of the challenges related to the radio protocols and procedures, the same considerations on the NR-Uu and F1 logical interfaces on the user and feeder links previously introduced hold.

3.2.3 Multi-Connectivity

3GPP studied the simultaneous Protocol Data Unit (PDU) session MC of a UE over terrestrial RAN and satellite-based NG-RAN and decided not to include it in Rel. 17 specifications. However, it does not preclude the deployment of a UE that may simultaneously run separate Registrations and PDU Sessions in NTN and TN with different Public Land Mobile Networks (PLMN).

The 5G system is expected to support service continuity between 5G terrestrial access network and 5G satellite access networks owned by the same operator or owned by two different operators having an agreement. In principle, NSA (Non standalone) operation between NTN and TN, such as running one leg connection with NTN and another leg connection with TN, is not precluded in standards, but it can be potentially challenging. Running Xn connections between an NTN gNB and a terrestrial gNB is itself very challenging due to the many constraints like UP flow control and other factors.

Figure 21. NTN architecture with Dual Connectivity provided through TN and NTN accesses with transparent (above) and regenerative (below) payloads.

NTN as currently considered does not support NSA with TN: even MR-DC (Multi Radio Dual Connectivity) and NR-to-NR Dual Connectivity (NR-NR DC) would be problematic. Thus, currently, NSA-based aspects (such as Xn mobility between NTN gNBs and terrestrial gNBs, MR-DC, secondary RAT data volume reporting, traces, etc.) are treated with low priority in 3GPP. A number of Xn specifications are not expected to need explicit updates for NTN, so such support is left for vendor implementation. It is expected the NG-based mobility should work to transition between NTN and TN. It is anticipated that NTN can interact with 5G, 4G, or even 3G terrestrial networks via legacy inter-RAT procedures. Detailed idle mode and connected mode procedures are currently left for vendor implementation, [27].

Figure 21 and Figure 22 show an example of DC with TN-NTN and NTN only access types, respectively. As already mentioned, in the former case the complexity is significant due to the need for properly synchronise and align the transmissions over two very different channels. In both cases, the Xn interface over SRI is needed to tightly coordinate the master and secondary gNBs. Moreover, it shall also be mentioned that the RAN might flexibly select either the NTN or the TN gNB as master node, with the other acting as secondary gNB.

Figure 22. NTN architecture with Dual Connectivity provided through two NTN accesses without (above) and with (below) functional split.

3.3 6G NTN: 3D ML-MO-MB architecture

Modern day transportation is growing more and more dependent on high speed transportation: not only planes, but trains as well have become pivotal in various aspects of daily life. Passengers often require access to the network while traveling, either on trains, or even on planes. The existing infrastructures based off Wi-Fi are often underperforming and unreliable, while the ground network are often in underserved areas. The small size of the ground 5G cells, comparable at most to 4G coverage, would also cause numerous handover requests as the vehicle passes through various cells.

A 3D Multi-Dimensional Multi-Layered Multi-Band (MD-ML-MB) NTN architecture, shown in Figure 23, would be a fitting solution to such an issue: while LEO satellites would cause similar handover challenges, even considering their large coverage, moving vehicles may interface with LEO satellites thanks to active antennas, or, to further reduce the handover and Doppler effect, the vehicle may interface with HAPS offering regional coverage for access to the network, while the data are relayed by the HAPS to LEO or GEO satellites, depending on the type of requested service, [23].

HAPS offer the opportunity for wide area access: their altitude allows for direct access by handheld devices, as well as the use of large antennas, and stationary coverage, collecting data on a large area

reducing the impact of handover for moving vehicles. Additionally, their stationary flight allows for a noticeable reduction of Doppler issues, as only the vehicle would be moving. The size of HAPS allows them to mount directive active antennas able to follow a LEO satellite in flight, granting a longer visibility, which can be further improved through ISLs.

The envisioned 3D ML-MO-MB system, also in line with the evolution of the normative work discussed in this document, shall support several key system requirements defining the characteristics of the non-terrestrial component in the overall infrastructure:

Figure 23. 6G NTN 3D Multi-Layer Multi-Orbit Multi-Band architecture.

- **Flexible allocation of the capacity to commensurate a varying traffic:** the satellite network infrastructure shall be able to adapt the overall capacity of the space segment to the traffic demand which is dynamic across the geographical coverage in terms of intensity, scenario, and audience. The intensity of the traffic depends on the connection density and the related bandwidth requirements. This also requires to adapt the feeder and inter nodes links capacity.
- **Extended coverage towards global services:** extended coverage compared to terrestrial mobile network, is an essential added value of satellite network components. Depending on the altitude and types of orbit of the NTN nodes, regional, worldwide, and even full Earth coverage can be achieved.
- **System sustainability:** great care shall be taken into consideration for:
 - the operation and end of life disposal (*e.g.*, de-orbiting) strategy of the space/aerial segment based on multiple flying nodes to prevent space junks, in-orbit collisions and impacts on astronomical observations;
 - the minimization of the overall carbon footprint (including the energy consumption) of the network infrastructure and especially the on-ground network nodes and user terminals;
 - the compliance with requirements on users' exposure to Electro Magnetic Fields (EMF).
- **Network resiliency through massive redundant routing:** the resiliency of the network is a crucial requirement given that 5G-A and 6G systems will be the cornerstone of the digital economy. To reinforce such resilience, the NTN component, subject to different natural and man-made disasters compared to the TN, can be added to increase the routing possibilities to

support the traffic generated/received by a terminal. In addition, when defined as a multi-dimensional and multi-layered infrastructure, composed of space-borne and air-borne flying nodes possibly interconnected by means of wireless and optical links the different routing possibilities to support the traffic can be maximised contributing to further increase the overall 6G system resiliency.

- **Security:** the support of logical slices, each used or operated by different stakeholders, requires high security to prevent eavesdropping and to ensure the integrity of the traffic. In addition, the integration of the 6G network component in the cloud also requires novel security architecture to protect the storage and the computing of data on board the different flying network nodes interconnected via temporary wireless links to form a dynamic network topology.
- **Service reliability through smart retransmission:** it shall be possible to ensure high reliability of the transmission of data in a given time slot by means of re-transmission techniques such as repetition, interleaving or power/coding dynamic adaptation.
- **Design to usage approach:** it is essential to also take into account installation and operational constraints in the design of the user terminals served by the non-terrestrial networks. The network infrastructure shall be designed to accommodate terminal constraints such as form factor, energy consumption, and usage conditions. The feasibility of being able to serve directly smart phones in indoor conditions should be considered although this may imply a reduced quality of service. When considering the automotive and drone market segments, the size and form factor of the terminal devices shall be adapted to the mounting constraints. For example, typical aperture size of 10–15 cm diameter shall be envisaged for acceptable footprint on vehicle and drone roofs. To the possible extent, fixed terminals shall be designed for self-installation on building roof tops.
- **Spectrum optimisation:** NTN is used as complementary to TN operations, and in separate locations when satellite operates in an adjacent channel/band of terrestrial network. For instance, NTN satellite UE is assumed to connect and transmit to the satellite when it is outside a Terrestrial Network operating in an adjacent channel/band. The satellite beam might still overlap the terrestrial network. Given the spectrum scarcity, it is necessary to design satellite network component able to co-exist with terrestrial network component.
- **Network infrastructure reconfigurability:** thanks to edge computing and storage resources on each network nodes (flying and on ground), it will be possible to configure the NTN component for the support of a given communication services optimising some parameters impacting the service such as the response delay, the bandwidth across the different wireless links involved and/or the energy consumption at ground and terminal level.
- **Seamless response time through MC between GSO and NGSO:** latency directly impacts the response time perceived by the users when accessing a service over a network infrastructure. In the context of NTN, it is proportional to the altitude of the flying network nodes. A reduced latency is critical for time-sensitive interactive applications such as gaming and electronic services trading but also internet access given that users gets rapidly frustrated when the web page is not immediately downloaded upon request. Typically, this severely penalises GSO-based networks. In such context, combining an access network based on GSO nodes with an access network based on (V)LEO nodes can become advantageous. It allows to benefit from the low latency of LEO based access network and from the large bandwidth that may be provided by GSO based access networks. This will allow to support a wide range of services characterised by different latency requirements, *e.g.*, eMBB and URLLC.

4 KEY ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES FOR NTN BEYOND 5G

Leveraging Rel. 17 NTN specifications discussed in Section 1, and targeting the services identified in Section 2, evolutions of both the available technologies (5G-A) and revolutionary concepts (6G) shall be developed for future NTN systems.

As previously discussed, service and capability enhancements are already being developed in the framework of Rel. 18. In particular, for mMTC services the evolution is being directed towards a performance improvement in discontinuous coverage and to deal with terminal mobility. As for eMBB, the following features are being addressed: i) network-based UE location determination; ii) coverage enhancements; iii) NR- NTN deployment above 10 GHz and support for VSAT/ESIM terminals; iv) NTN-TN and NTN-NTN mobility and service continuity enhancements.

Below, we report an overview of the candidate technologies and techniques for 5G-Advanced and 6G NTN. The former includes some of the solutions that were de-prioritised in Rel. 18 and which might be considered as candidate features for Rel. 19. For 6G, *i.e.*, Rel. 20 and beyond, more revolutionary concepts are expected to realise the proposed 3D ML-MO-MB NTN architecture. The list of candidate technologies for 5G-A and 6G NTN discussed below is summarised in Table 8.

Table 8. List of candidate technologies for 5G-A and 6G NTN.

System	Technique/technology
5G-A	MU-MIMO: standalone NTN node
	Multi-Connectivity and Carrier Aggregation
	Beam management and BWP association
	Duplexing
	L-band and higher frequency bands
	User Equipment
6G	NTN-TN and NTN-NTN mobility and service continuity
	MU-MIMO: multiple NTN nodes
	Waveform constraints and design
	Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning
	Inter-Satellite Links
	Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access
Refractive Intelligent Surfaces	

4.1 5G-Advanced

MU-MIMO: standalone NTN node

Satellite payloads are now equipped with flexible On-Board Processors (OBPs), which provide advanced capabilities to improve the link budget and response times, as well as allowing to move core network features on-board. In this context, the payload is actually part of the global network, *i.e.*, it allows the possibility to implement processing in the lower layers (gNB-DU), higher layers (full gNB), network functions as core network (*e.g.*, UP Function) or even edge computing, and in-space routing by also exploiting ISLs. The advanced processors, combined with active antenna arrays, offer the possibility to

Figure 24. Example of architecture for CF-MIMO NTN with a standalone NTN node.

continuously optimise the resource management by allocating the power/time/frequency/space resources to where they are required by means of user-centric beamforming, also known as Cell Free-MIMO (CF-MIMO). The implementation of these techniques in NTN is non-trivial due to the need for accurate Channel State Information (CSI) at the transmitter. This is even more critical when considering mobile UEs, *e.g.*, on fast moving platforms as airplanes or trains, and/or NGSO systems, with fast moving satellites.

To tackle the above challenges, the following solutions can be envisaged, [28]-[29]: i) exploiting the availability of advanced OBPs, the beamforming coefficients can be computed on-board, thus significantly reducing the impact of latency and CSI aging; ii) assuming that the UEs have GNSS capabilities, the CSI might be predicted by combining such information with the satellite ephemeris and/or by exploiting Machine Learning (ML) algorithms. The implementation of location-based, rather than CSI-based, solutions also allows to avoid potentially complex channel estimation procedures at the UEs, in which it might be difficult to estimate some of the coefficients due to the large Carrier-to-Interference Ratio (CIR) at the receiver. Another aspect to be taken into account is related to the actual traffic demand from the users, which can be significantly non-uniform across the service area. In such scenarios, regular beam lattices obtained with a predefined value of the radiation pattern at the beam edge might lead to a non-optimal resource distribution; by fully exploiting regenerative payloads and active antenna arrays, the OBP might be able to generate narrower beams in high traffic areas and wider beams in areas where the overall traffic request is more limited, [30]-[31], *i.e.*, to tailor the resource allocations to the on-ground “hot” and “cold” spots. In this framework, also mixed frequency reuse schemes can be envisaged, *i.e.*, cold spot areas to be served with 3 or 4 colour schemes and hot spot areas in full frequency reuse.

It is worthwhile highlighting that 3GPP NTN specifications already allow to implement MIMO with multiple beams per cell, *i.e.*, all of the beams belonging to the same cell can operate in full frequency reuse on their spectrum portion through MIMO. However, CF-MIMO for 5G-A and 6G should target more advanced solutions to further improve the system capacity, in which, [28]-[31]: i) user-centric beamforming is considered, *i.e.*, beams are generated towards the users without the need of a predefined beam; and ii) all users are served with the entire spectrum in full frequency reuse.

Notably, the exploitation of MIMO algorithms can lead to substantial benefits in terms of data rate, reliability, robustness to the UEs speed (as demonstrated in the cited literature), and latency (when the coefficients are computed on-board). Clearly, there are also several challenges, mainly related to the signalling overhead and difficulty in obtaining the CSI estimated (for CSI-based algorithms) and their aging mainly due to the satellite movement. In addition, scheduling, in particular when traffic-driven, might be challenging. Finally, for location-based solutions, it is worthwhile highlighting that a potential challenge is related to security. In fact, for their implementation it is required that the UEs’ locations are known, which can be not aligned with privacy and cyber-security regulations in all countries. In addition, it shall also be mentioned that the locations are not usually known at the gNB, while they are available in the 5GC. A possible solution might be that of sampling the entire coverage area in much smaller regions and then approximate the locations of the users in an area with its center, which was proposed for scheduling purposes in [32]. This would avoid the need for the exact location knowledge and, depending on how fine the spatial sampling is, it would still provide a good performance.

Multi-Connectivity and Carrier Aggregation

Multi-Connectivity (MC) and Carrier Aggregation (CA) are viable approaches to increase the user throughput and Quality of Experience (QoE) by means of spatial diversity between NGSO-NGSO and GSO-NGSO satellites, *i.e.*, satellites at potentially very different orbits as in the proposed 3D ML-MO-MB NTN architecture.

MC is a generalization of Dual Connectivity (DC), where a UE can be connected to two radio base stations simultaneously, that is, to a Master Node (MN) and a Secondary Node (SN); in MC, there could also be multiple SNs. The data that is to be sent to the UE first arrives to the MN. The MN can then decide to send the data to the UE or to forward it to the SN who will then send the data to the UE. MC can be used to enhance throughput and/or reliability, for example, when a UE is at a cell edge where

throughput requirements are not met, or a UE has a demand for URLLC. URLLC consists of, for example, telesurgery and automated traffic. MC is one of the candidate features for Rel. 19; in fact, it was specified for TNs as part of Rel. 15 in TS 37.340, [33], but it has not yet been addressed for NTN.

3GPP TR 38.821 includes information related to the introduction of MC in NTN, also providing the architectural aspects previously discussed in Section 3.2.3. Some potential challenges are identified as well. These include the following: i) with regenerative payloads, the F1 Air Interface between the gNB-CU and gNB-DU shall accommodate larger latencies compared to TN and it might need smart implementations to guarantee its persistence; ii) the Xn Air Interface is unaffected by the presence of the NTN, but the leg over F1 will need to adapt to the much longer RTTs; iii) the UP buffering in the node implementing the PDCP shall compensate for the different between the different links, i.e., in particular when TN-NTN MC is considered; and iv) the satellites' movement can lead to potentially frequent SN/MN handovers.

MC in NTNs is illustrated in Figure 25. It consists of a UE receiving transmissions from two separate transparent LEO satellites. While the different air interfaces were discussed in Section 3.2.3, this figure shows the 5G UP protocol stacks for both the gNBs and the UE. As mentioned above, the data that is to be sent to the UE first arrives at the MN's PDCP layer, which can then forward the data for the SN to send to the UE. The UE

Figure 25. MC illustration in NTN environment.

must be able to receive separate transmissions from the gNBs. The data is then combined at the PDCP layer. Both, the MN and the SN could host Service Data Adaption Protocol (SDAP) layers for each PDU session towards the UE, but in the figure, only the MN hosts an SDAP. The altitudes of LEO satellites can be 250-2000 km. In the figure, h refers to the altitudes of the satellites, whereas ε_1 and ε_2 to the elevation angles. The NLOS probability is higher with lower elevation angles, e.g., because of trees and buildings. The GWs serving the satellites can be the same, close to each other or they can even reside on different continents.

CA, initially introduced in LTE, is a technique in which multiple carriers are aggregated to serve the same UE; on the other hand, MC allows the same UE to be connected to multiple nodes simultaneously, increasing the transmission robustness and reliability. Intra-satellite CA is particularly important in high frequency bands to provide very large throughput or to increase the flexibility with frequency channel planning: smaller channels can improve the link budget and they can be aggregated if larger bandwidths are required. In this framework, the different propagation delays and/or network topologies between the various access nodes pose a challenge and shall be taken into account. Moreover, the system shall also handle different time and frequency compensations, as well as the optimised selection of the master node versus the secondary node. The main advantages of CA are enhanced throughput, inter-cell interference mitigation, and network deployment enhancement, [34]. CA can be achieved with intra-band contiguous, intra-band non-contiguous, or inter-band non-contiguous carriers. The maximum number of aggregated carriers for both downlink and uplink is 16, as defined in Rel. 15. On the UE side, using intra-band contiguous carriers does not require updates to hardware, [35]. On the other hand, when using intra-/inter-band non-contiguous carriers, the carriers cannot be treated as a single signal and thus multiple receivers are required.

Beam management and BWP association

Beam management can be defined as a set of Layer 1 (PHY) and Layer 2 (MAC) procedures to establish and retain an optimal beam pair for good connectivity. A beam pair consists of a transmit beam and a corresponding receive beam in one link direction. Several proposals for beam management in NTN were discussed during the study phase, [4]. Since a convergence to one particular solution was not possible at the conclusion of the study phase, it was agreed that 3GPP Rel. 15 and 16, [4], [36]-[37], are

considered as a baseline for beam management and Bandwidth Part (BWP) operations in NTN and they should be discussed further when future specifications are developed.

NR Beamforming needs channel knowledge at the transmitter. Regular beam management operations are based on the control messages which are periodically exchanged between the gNB and the UE. In NTN, it will be challenging to implement an optimal and dynamic/fast beamforming towards the users. There are different reasons for that: FDD is assumed for core specification work for NR-NTN. As in FDD there is no channel reciprocity, channel information cannot be obtained from UL SRS. Also, the propagation delay in NTN may impact the validity of Layer 1 beam measurement. Furthermore, the generated satellite beams are with a large size (tens or maybe hundreds of km).

Thus, a different approach should be taken in NTN: the gNB should operate on a set of predefined satellite beams in UL and DL. For Earth-fixed beam scenarios, beams are static and do not move (from the UE perspective), but beams should be steered to cover Earth-fixed cell area. In case of LEO-based Earth-moving cells, the satellite beams are moving on the ground and the users are jumping from beam to beam. From our perspective, there are mainly 3 options which can be considered for the mapping of NR beams and NR cells to the satellite beams:

- Option (1), which might be considered as a baseline consisting of a one-to-one mapping of NR cells to satellite beams. In this case, NR beamforming is not used; the cells are single NR beam cells and NR beam management operation is not needed.
- Option (2), with a multi-beam satellite and a single NR beam cell, with cell splitting. In this case, two or more satellite beams are used for the same PHY Cell Identity (PCI). NR beamforming is not used. This option can be useful to split the NR cell across several satellite beams (to extend cell coverage). Regular beam management operation (beam indication, beam measurements and reporting, beam recovery, tracking and refinement) is not used. The beam level mobility is not needed for the UE mobility within the cell.
- Option (3), with a multi-beam satellite and a multi-beam NR cell, in which there are multiple NR beams per NR cell (typically 4 NR beams/cell in FR1). With this option, the same cell (*i.e.*, PCI) is mapped to two or more satellite beams. Each NR beam is transmitted using a satellite beam or multiple satellite beams. Option (3) shall be used with beam management operation.

Figure 27. Single satellite beam per cell.

Figure 26. Multiple satellite beams per cell with cell-splitting.

Figure 28. Multiple satellite beams per cell with multiple NR beams

Beam level mobility is to be used to control the UE connected mode mobility instead of the handover procedure, which is mainly beneficial with Earth-moving beams as beam level mobility does not require explicit RRC signalling to be triggered (it is dealt with at lower layers and RRC is not required to know which beam is being used at a given point in time). Thus, the UE moves inside the cell, handled by beam management without extra RRC signalling overhead. However, in NTN, when we use several beams per cell (as in Option 3), we increase *ipso facto* the cell size. Therefore, the cell Air Interface capacity limit should be taken into account. As a consequence, deploying multi-beam cell and using beam management might not be applicable to all NTN deployment scenarios.

Duplexing

Notably, the implementation of TDD has two major drawbacks: i) the need for a Guard Interval (GI); and ii) coexistence aspects between neighbouring cells. As for the former, TDD operation requires the introduction of guard time intervals each time a DL-to-UL transmissions switch occurs, [3]. The duration of the GI interval is mainly driven by the maximal RTT experienced in the cell. Therefore, the interval needed for NTN systems can reach prohibitive values which lead to a very low spectral efficiency. This effect is particularly detrimental in GSO systems. The coexistence of neighboring cells operated in TDD mode in the same band is usually supported by inter/intra-operator synchronization, in order to avoid interference between the DL and UL transmissions of different cells. This means that all gNBs need to have the same DL/UL configurations and frame synchronization. If such precaution is not implemented, harmful interference can be experienced leading to a significant performance loss. For TDD operated NTN, the scenarios where a satellite interferes with another satellite receiving transmissions from the ground can be predicted, but it would require inter/intra operator coordination, especially where a multi-constellation 5G service is deployed. It is worthwhile noticing that the interference introduced in these scenarios is, in general, less harmful compared to the terrestrial case. However, the coordination complexity to avoid them is undoubtedly of a higher level; this is motivated by the difference of geometric layout associated to the TN and NTN deployments. Finally, in case of TN-NTN TDD coordination, the frame synchronization between one satellite cell and a terrestrial cell can be achieved. However, achieving frame synchronization level between the satellite cell and several terrestrial cells characterized by significantly different propagation delays with respect to the satellite seems unfeasible. Unfortunately, it is very likely the satellite cell overlaps with more than one terrestrial cell; moreover, these terrestrial cells may be located in a very heterogeneous way within the satellite coverage.

Rel. 17 NTN specifications focus on transparent payload architectures with FDD systems where all UEs are assumed to have GNSS capabilities. Most of the existing satellite systems operate in the frequency bands designated for FDD mode, with defined transmit direction. These specifications support NR based satellite access deployed in FR1 bands serving handheld devices for global service continuity. In NTN, it is preferable to use full-duplex techniques, in which the DL and UL phases occur simultaneously. With half-duplex communications, there are challenges in switching between the DL and UL phases due to the high latency (compared to TNs). Typically, half-duplex techniques are used in satellite communications using satellites in low orbits (*e.g.*, LEO, HAPS), where latency is easier to manage. In particular, an NB-IoT UE only needs to support half-duplex operations, while eMTC can support both full-duplex FDD and half-duplex FDD. As for NTN, it currently supports NR full-duplex in FR1. Half-duplex FDD mode in NTN is not currently discussed within 3GPP. For terrestrial networks, however, half-duplex FDD operation has been classified as follows, [38]:

- Type A: half-duplex FDD operation, a GI is introduced by the UE by not receiving the last part of a downlink sub-frame immediately preceding an uplink sub-frame from the same UE.
- Type B: half-duplex FDD operation, GIs, each referred to as a half-duplex guard sub-frame, are introduced by the UE by
 - not receiving a downlink sub-frame immediately preceding an uplink sub-frame from the same UE;
 - not receiving a downlink sub-frame immediately following an uplink sub-frame from the same UE.

L-band and higher frequency bands

The frequency bands n256 (S-band) and n255 (L-band) are new FR1 NR NTN frequency bands for satellite operation which were introduced in Rel. 17 technical specification (see Section 1.1) for FR1 frequency range. These frequency bands are used for direct connectivity to handheld UEs.

Both Mobile Satellite System (MSS) S and L bands are limited in terms of available bandwidth and, thereby, a new WI was proposed as part of Rel. 18 to define enhancements for NG-RAN based NTN in order to support new scenarios to cover NR-NTN deployments in frequency bands above 10 GHz. The following assumptions are taken a baseline for NR-NTN deployments in frequency bands above 10

GHz, [39]: i) to consider GSO and NGSO satellite access (ESIM scenarios for NGSO in Ka-band are excluded from this WI); ii) target fixed and mobile VSATs, without excluding that additional NTN UE classes compared to those reported in TR 38.821 might be defined; iii) FDD is considered for NTN in FR2, while TNs operate in TDD; iv) the ITU-R harmonised Ka-band spectrum will be considered as a reference; and v) co-existence between overlapping TN and NTN bands is not considered in the WI. For further information see for instance R4-2215352 with discussions on Ka-band NTN-TN NR adjacent band coexistence scenarios, [40].

The following studies will be performed in the framework of this WI:

- the following PHY parameters shall be chosen from the existing FR1 and FR2 sets: time relationship related enhancement, sub-carrier spacing for different UL/DL signals and channels, and the PRACH configuration index for FDD operations above 10 GHz;
- within RAN4, the regulations and adjacent channel coexistence scenarios will be analysed to identify an NTN example band. Then, additional bands might be introduced following a release-independent approach. To this aim, the harmonised ITU-R Ka-band will be considered as a reference, as mentioned above. Clearly, it shall be guaranteed that the introduced NTN bands do not impact the existing specifications and do not cause any degradation to networks in the 3GPP specific terrestrial bands adjacent to the NTN ones. In that, it is assumed that the NTN-TN adjacent band coexistence will be performed at the harmonized Ka band edges. The outcome is expected to be applicable to all NTN-TN adjacent band scenarios (if any) in the whole Ka-band range where applicable and regulations allow. In addition, it is highlighted that the definition of NTN band(s) above 10 GHz does not change the current FR1/FR2 definition, nor automatically apply to future terrestrial bands defined in this frequency region;
- the TX/RX requirements for the SAN and various VSAT UE classes (*i.e.*, not limited to the 60 cm aperture antenna case) will be specified for the identified example band;

However, the coexistence scenarios cases will most probably consider worst cases in terms of VSAT characteristics; see for instance R4-2215348 for VSAT UE characteristics and initial simulation parameters, [42]. Moreover, as agreed at 3GPP TSG-RAN WG4 Meeting #105 in November 2022, with respect to the way forward (WF) for above 10 GHz band definition and system parameters (see R4-2220239, [43]), the following Ka-band configurations are considered as starting point:

- n511 with consideration of US/FCC regulations;
- n512 with consideration of CEPT regulations;
- n510 with consideration of US/FCC regulations;

with the following considerations:

- DL: 17.7-20.2 GHz (n512, n511, n510);
- UL: 27.5-30.0 GHz (n512), 28.35-30.0 GHz (n511), 27.5-28.35 GHz (n510).

User Equipment

As discussed in Section 1.1, Rel. 17 NTN is targeting direct connectivity to smartphones with omnidirectional and realistic antenna gain (-5.5 dBi) which, combined with current maximum 30 – 34 MHz total available bandwidth and 23 dBm NTN UE power limitation, may result in low spectrum efficiency and low throughput user experience. Therefore, VSAT user equipment with higher antenna gain and transmission power, operating in higher frequency bands (*e.g.*, Ku/Ka and/or Q/V frequency bands) with larger available channel bandwidths are of interest for 3GPP Rel. 18.

In addition, support of High Power UE (HPUE), *e.g.*, 26 dBm transmission power, in NTN was discussed at the RAN#97 meeting (September 2022) for FR1. Although all companies agree that HPUEs would help in the NTN coverage enhancement, no agreement could be achieved yet. It shall be noticed that the introduction of HPUEs would require RAN4 to study the feasibility for HPUE in NTN bands (*i.e.*, review of the coexistence evaluations). The intention is to support HPUE in NTN, *i.e.*, UE Power

Class 2, double the maximum output power previously defined by Power Class 3 to allow the UE to transmit with up to 26 dBm in selected NTN bands, which will provide significant advantages for users and carriers: i) increase the UE uplink transmit power to afford significant uplink coverage extension, thus reducing the performance gap between DL and UL; and ii) increase the UE throughput, especially for verticals, *e.g.*, public safety applications. It is worthwhile highlighting that HPUEs should be investigated also in terms of EMF limitations.

NTN-TN and NTN-NTN mobility and service continuity

Enhancements related to the NTN-NTN mobility are included as Rel. 18 features and will focus on cell reselection, handover, and signalling minimisation.

One of the key differences between TN and NTN is the large satellites' speed and the larger cell size. While in TN and GSO systems the cell service area can be considered as quite stable, for NGSO the beams are moving (Earth-moving beams) or they track and illuminate a given area for a limited period of time (Earth-fixed beams). Handover is primarily triggered by the terminal movement (and potentially targeting for VSAT) in GSO systems, but large propagation delay without enhancements to, *e.g.*, the number of messages causes long disruptions to service continuity. NGSO constellations on the other hand can help with the propagation delay and path losses enabling the usage of handheld terminals with omnidirectional antennas but causing major challenges with the fast movement of the coverage areas and potentially frequent periodical handovers and measurements of neighbour cells.

It is generally presumed that NTN will be deployed on separate carriers not sharing frequency with TNs. LEO satellites may move up to 7.56 km per second and serve up to 65519 UEs per cell and, according to TR 38.821, parameters may serve a user in a cell with 50 km diameter for 6.61 seconds, [43]. Therefore, UE mobility from an NTN-to-NTN handover point of view is a relatively small factor in the case of NGSO constellations with Earth-moving cells, [44]. The focus on service continuity for NGSO satellites is therefore largely on making the UEs shift fluently between NTN cells due to the movement of the satellites. The main issues for handovers between NTN cells are: i) the UE should know which cell it makes a handover into, and for that purpose utilizing current functionalities the UE would require to make both inter- and intra-frequency measurements, extending the required functionalities of an NTN UE and increasing its power consumption; and ii) the handover related RRC messaging, and its following Random Access procedure, are resource-intensive, requiring time and pushing the control channel easily beyond its limits with a large cell size and a high number of users. For instance in the worst case a LEO satellite with a fully loaded cell would require about 10000 handovers per second.

For the former issue, the excessive measurements required for deciding the target cell of handover cause an issue assuming legacy measurement principles; some potential solutions include, [4], [37]-[62]: i) reporting the UE location to improve the handover decision, which however could cause privacy issues; ii) let the satellite send its reference location and a distance threshold, so that the UE initiates the measurements for the next cell when it exceeds the threshold; iii) extend the previous solution to include also neighbouring cells; and iv) broadcast ephemeris information of close-by satellites with reference locations and time estimates so that the UE can predict when the current serving satellite becomes unavailable, [37], or a neighbour satellite becomes the potential next serving cell, [46], or a time-based trigger per UE. In addition, also the number of measured cells and carriers needs to be limited to limit both the unusable time for primary cell connection and power consumption. As for the second issue, several optimizations are suggested to, among the others: i) reduce both the messages and delays for signalling; ii) indicate the target cell currently requires a lot of relatively large individual messages for each terminal, resulting in contributions suggesting 2-step handover, [43], group handover mechanisms, including multiple target cells in RRC reconfiguration message under certain conditions, [44], or possibly moving part of the RRC reconfiguration message content to broadcast messages; iii) let the network transfer as much of the UE context between the source and target gNB as possible so signalling overhead between UE and gNB is reduced. Conditional reconfiguration or handover mechanisms are also suggested for optimizing handover resource consumption on the network side. However, it is also noted that UE mobility might invalidate conditional time-based handover for Earth moving cells, [45].

domains. Another aspect worth to highlight is that the connection to the 5GC is being routed by a satellite, which can potentially be at any orbit (GSO or NGSO). However, this represents a worst-case scenario, since the swarm might be on an orbital location from which a direct connection to a serving GW is possible. The additional challenges posed by distributed CF-MIMO algorithms lead to considering such solutions as a possible candidate for 6G NTN, rather than 5G-A as the standalone case.

Waveform constraints and design

In terms of standardization, 5G-A systems are being finalised with the on-going Rel. 18 activities and it is not expected that significant modifications related to the Physical layer will be introduced in Rel. 19. However, there might be room for the design of novel or enhanced waveforms for 6G systems. In this context, two approaches, not necessarily mutually exclusive, can be envisaged: i) design a waveform in which the minimisation of the Peak-to-Average Power Ratio (PAPR) is considered as a key constraint; and ii) design a completely new waveform. As for the latter, below we focus on the recently introduced Orthogonal Time Frequency Space (OTFS) modulation.

Notably, high PAPR causes a significant power inefficiency and, thus, throughput losses; this aspect was already reported in Rel. 17, but for the moment being, despite its critical importance in terms of commercial viability and system capacity, it has not yet been addressed. This issue has been identified both above and below 6 GHz, but due to typical payload architectures it is more significant above 10 GHz. In particular, in Rel. 17 it was identified that the efficiency of power amplifiers decreases for increasing frequencies towards 100 GHz, [63]. Moreover, for transponder configurations with a small number (*i.e.*, less than 3- 4) of OFDM channels per High Power Amplifier (HPA), the throughput degradation may be severe. In this context, it is also worthwhile highlighting that PAPR alone is not a sufficient metric. The Out-Of-Band-Emission (OOBE) is also a significant player even in configurations with a large number of carriers per HPA, where the carrier PAPR is less problematic. In [64], numerical simulations were performed to evaluate the performance degradation with a single carrier per transponder. Such losses are in the 2.5-6.5 dB range; this analysis also shows that the total degradation is independent of the selected modulation and amplifier type. It should also be noticed that the high power fluctuation of the CP-OFDM waveform affects all payloads in the forward link due to gain compensation/compression that may be necessary to normalise the PAPR to some extent even at lower frequency bands. In this framework, the uplink already enables DFT- s-OFDM which features very low PAPR requirements and hence is comparable to the DVB-RCS2 Multi-Frequency Time Division Multiple Access (MF-TDMA) waveform; however, it is not sure whether this will be implemented in mmWave bands. Some preliminary analyses showing the performance of different variants of the OFDM waveform, namely DFT-s-W- OFDM, W-OFDM, DT-s-f-OFDM, and f-OFDM, are reported in [65], with different numerologies and OBO values. Here, it is shown how the different numerologies significantly impact the performance; moreover, it is also shown how large sub- carrier spacings can actually accommodate the large Doppler shifts in NGSO systems. In addition to PAPR and OOBE, the following enhancements can be considered at waveform level: i) reduced PRACH format to allow multiple PRACH transmissions in the same beam as well as extended link margin; ii) non-orthogonal schemes to increase the number of terminals that can be simultaneously served; and iii) Coordinated Multi- Point (CoMP) transmissions to increase peak user data rate.

Recently, an increasing amount of research attention has been dedicated to designing new modulation waveforms and schemes for high-mobility communications in next-generation wireless networks, [66]. A new two-dimensional (2D) modulation scheme, namely OTFS, [67], has been proposed as a promising candidate for high-mobility communications. In OTFS, information is modulated in the Delay-Doppler (DD) domain rather than in the time-frequency (TF) domain of classic OFDM modulation, providing a strong delay and Doppler-resilience, whilst enjoying the potential of full diversity, [67], which is the key for supporting reliable communications. Moreover, OTFS modulation can transform a time-variant channel into a 2D quasi-time-invariant channel in the DD domain, where its attractive properties can be exploited. Operating in the DD domain can be exploited to facilitate efficient channel estimation and data detection in terms of: i) separability, as introducing the Doppler domain allows us to separate the propagation paths experiencing an identical delay; ii) stability, since only the drastic change of

propagation path lengths and moving speeds may cause channel variations in the DD domain; and iii) compactness, since the channel response has a more compact DD domain support.

The application of the OTFS principles in NTN is still in its infancy. The authors in [68] investigated the reliability performance for the OTFS based downlink LEO satellite transmission with the aid of UAV cooperation. The authors then compared the OTFS scheme with OFDM in terms of outage probability and observed that in the downlink LEO-Satellite transmission, OTFS scheme can outperform OFDM scheme as long as the outage probability is smaller than 0.5. In [69], the OTFS enabled NOMA for mMTC applied over the LEO satellite is investigated. In particular, the authors propose a grant-free access system, where OTFS is introduced to tackle with the notable Doppler shift by Doppler diversity, rather than pre-compensation. In [70], the joint channel estimation and device activity detection in the grant-free random access systems, where a large number of IoT devices intend to communicate with a low-earth orbit satellite in a sporadic way, have been explored. In addition, the massive MIMO with OTFS modulation is adopted to combat the dynamics of the terrestrial satellite link.

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning

Today, satellite communications still heavily rely on human intervention. However, in the proposed 3D ML-MO-MB architecture, the potentially large speed of the satellites (in particular LEO/VLEO) and to the heterogeneity in the global network due to the deployment of satellites on multiple orbits, aerial elements (drones/HAPS/UAV), and ground elements, the system optimisation shall be performed in a highly dynamic environment; as such, human operations alone might not be sufficient anymore.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) are widely recognised as the most promising solution in such dynamic and information-rich contexts in wireless communications. An interesting review on possible applications of AI/ML concepts to NTN is provided in [71]-[72] and the references therein. Some of the most interesting are listed hereafter:

- **RRM:** RRM algorithms, including beamforming and Beam Hopping (BH), are one of the most likely applications. With respect to beamforming, AI solutions can be related to two main aspects: i) channel estimation, discussed below; and ii) scheduling. Notably, scheduling in beamformed NTN systems is non-trivial, since the UE performance can only be known after the beamforming matrix has been computed, *i.e.*, after the scheduler selected the UEs to be served; thus, this information cannot be exploited a priori to optimise the scheduler and often iterative (computationally intensive) solutions need to be used. In this framework, supervised (regression) or unsupervised (clustering) ML algorithms can be evaluated to identify the best scheduling options based on ancillary information, *e.g.*, user location and/or traffic requests and satellite ephemeris. BH emerged as a promising technique to achieve a significant flexibility in adjusting the capacity provisioning to the traffic requests, in particular in traffic-driven implementations. The optimisation of the BH illumination plan is often formulated as an optimisation problem, solved through Genetic Algorithms (GA) or heuristic iterative solutions. The major challenge in such approaches is related to the identification of the global optimum instead of local optima when the search space is large, *i.e.*, with a large number of beams.
- **Channel modelling:** accurate channel estimates are fundamental in RRM algorithms and to assess the system performance in order to optimise its design. In this framework, some recent studies have exploited satellite/aerial images to derive approximate channel parameters, such as the standard deviation of the shadowing loss and the path loss exponent or even the RSRP. When image-based algorithms are implemented, a typical approach is that of exploiting Convolutional NN (CNN). The implementation of image-based solutions might be not feasible for NGSO systems, due to the rapidly changing environment for each satellite which would require a huge amount of images to be analysed in real-time, thus also introducing a significant overhead. In this framework, the possibility to implement linear/non-linear regression algorithms and NNs can be considered.
- **Traffic forecasting and congestion prediction:** traffic forecasting is a proactive solution aiming at ensuring the communication reliability and high-quality. The capability to predict the traffic behaviour is critical in relevant SatCom applications, congestion control, dynamic

routing, dynamic channel allocation, network planning, and network security. Satellite network traffic is self-similar and demonstrates long-range-dependence which should be taken into account. Traffic forecasting models for terrestrial networks based on self-similarity have a high computational complexity. An efficient traffic forecasting design for satellite networks is thus required and AI/ML solutions provide a viable approach.

- **Anomaly detection:** current anomaly detection approaches are mainly based on the comparison of the instantaneous telemetry/traffic readings with static thresholds. However, there is a huge amount of data that can be downlinked from the satellites and it might be difficult to properly analyse it in real-time with a static approach. In this context, labelling the data as corresponding to normal or anomalous event, AI and ML can yield obvious benefits.
- **Interference management:** managing interference is an essential task to preserve high-quality and reliable communications; it includes interference detection, classification, and minimisation or suppression (if needed). Currently, interference management is performed by means of human intervention by performing exhaustive analyses, which can take up even days. However, the detection of anomalous error rates, power spectral densities, or user experience, among the others, can be automated by means of AI and ML.
- **Flexible payload optimisation:** a further step compared to RRM and interference management is that of autonomously reconfigure the payload in terms of power allocation per radiating element, bandwidth allocation, and beamforming, given a sudden change in the interference power level of a certain coverage area. The updated optimal payload configuration shall be clearly provided in a very short time interval, thus ruling out human intervention.
- **Telemetry mining:** one of the earliest and simplest techniques used in telemetry analysis is limit checking, which is based on defining precise ranges for each feature to be monitored (*e.g.*, temperature or current), and then observe the variance of each feature to detect out-of-range events. The main advantage of this approach is its simplicity. However, current complex spacecrafts, and their advanced applications, challenge this approach. Analysing, monitoring, and interpreting huge telemetry parameters could be impossible due to the high complexity of the data. Processing the potentially vast amount of data obtained through the satellite telemetry is fundamental to detect and minimise the risk of failures. Mining the telemetry data is based on the research for correlations, pattern recognition, and anomaly detection. As such, it is a scenario in which classification and clustering algorithms can be particularly useful.
- **Remote sensing:** remote sensing is the process of extracting information from an area, object, or phenomenon by processing its reflected and emitted radiation generally from satellite or aircraft. It has a quite wide range of applications in multiple fields, including land surveying, geography, geology, ecology, meteorology, oceanography, military and communication. AI/ML algorithms for pattern and image recognition, classification, and object detection are a natural solution for this type of service.

In the proposed ML-MO-MB NTN architecture, an extremely heterogeneous set of nodes can be part of the network operating at different orbits and bands. In general, AI and ML algorithms require training before they can be applied to new observations and scenarios. In this context, one possibility could be that of training and deploying the algorithm at each node, as shown in Figure 30; this solution would lead to an algorithm that is excellently tailored to the environment in which the node is operating, but it would also require a significant complexity on-board (this might even be not feasible for reduced complexity nodes, as drones).

Another possibility is that of collecting the observations from the nodes covering a given geographical area, training the algorithm at an on-ground network element with sufficient computational capabilities, and then upload the trained algorithm to the nodes in the area. While the nodes are operating with the trained AI/ML algorithm, new observations can be provided to the training network entity, which can further improve the performance, *e.g.*, by means of reinforcement learning or additional training steps with hyper-parameter optimization. This is shown in the high-level Figure 31; the observations provided from the on-ground users or the NTN nodes to the AI/ML entity can be extremely heterogeneous, *e.g.*, telemetry data, traffic demands, locations, gyroscope data, etc. It is worthwhile highlighting that the network entity training the AI/ML algorithms can be managing multiple coverage areas, as shown in the figure. The extension of the managed area, and their number, per AI/ML entity is clearly a parameter that can be reconfigured or optimised as well.

Clearly, the above list of potential applications for AI/ML is limited to the most relevant, but other applications of AI and ML algorithms can be designed and deployed.

Inter-Satellite Links

An architecture based on a regenerative satellite payload will allow the possibility to implement processing in the lower layers (gNB-DU), higher layers (full gNB), network functions as core network (*e.g.*, User Plane Function) or even edge computing, and in-space routing by exploiting Inter-satellite (ISL) relaying between satellites, [23]. For the latter, it shall be noticed that ISLs can be between two satellites of the same constellation (intra-/inter-orbital plane), between two satellites of different constellations/orbits (*e.g.*, between LEO and MEO satellites). Some scenarios based on regenerative payload architectures have already been studied by 3GPP and are documented in 3GPP TR 38.821: they involve moving all or part of the gNB functionality on board the satellite. It seems likely that 3GPP might discuss the adoption of a regenerative NTN architecture including ISLs in Rel. 19. Figure 32 illustrates a regenerative payload: the payload processes the SRI protocol between the service link and the feeder link, with potential use of inter-satellite links depending on the chosen architecture.

Inter-satellite links may operate in RF frequency or optical bands. They will allow to provide service in

Figure 30. High-level representation of AI/ML operations in the ML-MO-MB NTN architecture: on-board training.

Figure 31. High-level representation of AI/ML operations in the ML-MO-MB NTN architecture: on-ground training.

Figure 33. Distributed gNB for NGSO satellites, [73].

Figure 32. ISLs where relevant through RF frequency or optical bands.

areas where there are no NTN-gateways and provide coverage of remote areas like oceans as shown in Figure 33. The route taken between the GW and the satellite may thus change, adding or removing inter-satellite links to reach the GW. Impact of ISL SWITCH-OVER should therefore be studied. It is worth noting that the World Radiocommunications Conference 2023 (WRC-23) is assumed to tackle the regulatory aspects for inter-satellite links.

Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access

Non-Orthogonal Multiple Access (NOMA) schemes allow to transmit data layers of different UEs simultaneously over the same transmission resources. At the transmitter, the signal of multiple UEs can be superimposed over the same time, frequency and/or spatial resource. The transmitter is characterized by MA (Multiple Access) signature and features, which are typically used to differentiate the users. At the receiver, the signal from different UEs can be detected correctly by proper receivers, such as SIC (Successive Interference Cancellation) receivers. Compared to Orthogonal Multiple Access (OMA), the main advantages of NOMA are the support of higher connection density (*i.e.*, number of users per cell) and increased spectral efficiency. NOMA can be used to make the number of simultaneous user connections increase significantly which benefits the mMTC scenario. Moreover, it can also enhance the spectral efficiency, so that the multiple user channel capacity can be achieved. Besides, NOMA techniques generally do not rely on the knowledge of short-term CSI which makes the system robust against the mobility of UE and CSI feedback latency.

Figure 34. Scenarios for NOMA, [74].

In terms of use cases, NOMA can be used in three major use scenarios of 5G, [74]. Figure 34 shows the characteristics of each scenario, highlighting those that are most relevant to NOMA operation and the corresponding performance benefits are listed in Table 9.

Table 9. Summary of the performance benefit of NOMA techniques.

Scenario		Benefits
URLLC (grant-free)		- More efficient use of SPS allocated resources - Complexity reduction of receiver
mMTC (grant-free)		- Higher connection density per physical resource - Reduced latency, signalling overhead and power consumption
eMBB	Case 1: grant-free	- Efficient resource utilization - Reduced latency, signalling overhead and power consumption
	Case 2: grant-based	- Higher cell throughput, especially when # Rx antennas is small - Complexity reduction of receiver

In [75], the conventional 4-step random access scheme for the satellite IoT system is simplified. To reduce latency, the scheme carries out access signalling and data transmission simultaneously instead of using multiple rounds of signalling interaction. However, the above operation brings collisions between users. Thus, the authors propose to use NOMA to solve the information of devices at the time of the collision and improve transmission reliability, by means of a grant-free transmission transceiver for satellite IoT. From the view of the receiver side, the satellite base station does not have any prior information in the grant-free transmission. Therefore, the receiver needs to be set to asynchronous blind multi-user detection.

The main processing steps of the receiver include blind sequence identification, blind MMSE de-spreading, channel equalization and decoding, joint channel estimation and interference cancellation, and delay alignment.

Through simulations, it was demonstrated that the proposed scheme can achieve an improved Block Error Rate (BLER) performance compared with the conventional scheme, especially under the condition of high SNR. Therefore, their approach ensures transmission reliability while reducing random access latency and is suitable for satellite IoT systems.

The authors in [76] consider the existing NOMA schemes. They include the interleave division multiple access (IDMA), pattern division multiple access (PDMA), sparse code multiple access (SCMA), power domain non-orthogonal multiple access (PD-NOMA), and multi-user shared access (MUSA), as typical examples. Among them, the SCMA scheme, evolved from the low density signature for code division multiple access (LDS-CDMA), is taken as the most promising candidate with good performance and high overload rate. This scheme distinguishes different users through the predefined codebooks. Because of the indistinguishable power in one beam, the SCMA is more applicable for the LEO satellite communication. The available research on the SCMA mainly focuses on two aspects: one is the codebook design and the other is the multiuser detection. The core of this codebook design is to reduce the number of points with large power in the superposed constellation. The operations can be summarized as follows. First, the signal points with large power are reassigned to the points with small power to construct a low-PAPR mother constellation. Then, proper rotations are performed on the designed constellation to obtain different users' unique codebooks and maximize the Euclidean distance of the projection points with the largest power among the users colliding in a resource. Therefore, an optimized codebook design with low PAPR is got.

Simulation results show that compared with the 16-point SCMA mother constellation (called T16QAM), the proposed constellation called R12 and the constellation R4 can achieve lower PAPR and better performance. Meanwhile, they can lower computational complexity as well.

In [77], the authors propose a Superimposed Pilots Code Domain NOMA (SP CD-NOMA) Random access protocol in the uplink-oriented mMTC of Satellite Integrated Networks (SINs), aiming at satisfying the requirement of massive connectivity. Then, considering that the perfect CSI is unavailable due to the channel estimation error, they introduce an Iterative Channel Estimation (ICE) algorithm based on Ridge Regression (RR) to alleviate the effect of channel estimation error. Moreover, they derive the expressions of outage probability and throughput under successive joint decoding (SJD) and successive interference cancellation (SIC) algorithms, respectively.

In the proposed system model, the SAP utilize the SP sequences to detect activated UEs and obtain their CSI. The details of the uplink uncoordinated SP CD-NOMA scheme are shown as follows.

- **step 0:** in a certain time slot, a subset of UEs in total devices are activated and each activated UE sends an access request to the SAP for data transmission;
- **step 1:** the SAP detects the activated UEs and determines the number of pilots concentrated, then SAP broadcasts the pilot set to each activated UEs. Each pilot is orthogonal and corresponding to different codebooks;
- **step 2:** each activated UE randomly selects a pilot and superimposes on its data sequence with an optimal power coefficient, then each activated UE performs access to the SAP;
- **step 3:** the SAP can obtain the CSI of singleton UEs by utilizing the ICE algorithm and identifies the collision based on the received power level of pilots. The collided signals as regarded as interference, and then the SAP utilizes SIC or SJD to recover the non-colliding UEs.

The simulation results showed that the SP scheme can bring performance improvements than RP scheme in the uplink CD-NOMA for SIN. Moreover, in terms of OP and achievable throughput, SJD outperforms SIC across a wide range of code rate.

Refractive Intelligent Surfaces

A Reflecting Intelligent Surface (RIS), also known as Reconfigurable Smart Surface (RSS), is a thin meta-surface integrated with passive electronic components/switches that allows to control and manipulate the wireless signals that impinge on its surface, [78]. They can be used to modify the amplitude/phase of the signals, thus allowing to re-direct it towards desired directions. In terrestrial

networks, the exploitation of RISs has been extensively assessed (also including preliminary prototypes and industrial demonstrations), while its application to NTN is still in its very infancy.

In [79], link budget aspects for platforms including drones, HAPS, and LEO satellites implementing RIS are discussed, with both far-field and near-field models; this link budget analysis is also performed taking into account the characteristics of 3GPP channels. In [80], it was observed that most of the research activities related to RIS was focused on the full reflection of the signals, *i.e.*, no refraction through the meta-surface, and on the assumption that both the transmitters and the receivers were on the same side of the RIS (in line with the assumption of pure reflection). Thus, the authors focus on refracting RIS, in which all incident signals can pass through the surface, allowing to reconstruct the signals sent from the satellite indoor, which would be otherwise blocked. Finally, in [81], the implementation of RIS-assisted communications in GEO systems is proposed; in particular, this system envisages both a direct link and a RIS-reflected link arriving at the UE. A joint optimisation problem is formulated to define the optimal power allocation and reflecting phase shift design.

CONCLUSIONS

5G networks are being deployed all over the globe and the economy and society are already benefitting from the provided services. To fully **unleash their potential**, 5G-Advanced systems are already being designed; moreover, targeting **further enhanced capabilities and the convergence of the physical, human, and digital worlds**, the definition of the 6G vision has begun.

In this framework, leveraging the success of their integration in Rel. 17, it is globally recognised that NTN will play a pivotal role in future fully integrated systems.

In this White Paper, we provided an extensive overview of the normative activities for 3GPP NTN, including both the current Rel. 17 specifications and the activities that are currently being performed for 5G-Advanced in Rel. 18. In addition, we also discussed our vision for future 6G NTN systems, proposing a **3D Multi-Layer Multi-Orbit Multi-Band architecture providing a full and harmonised unification of the terrestrial and non-terrestrial network infrastructures**.

Current 5G services via satellite, eMBB-s, mMTC-s, and HRC-s have been discussed and a vision on future services for 5G-Advanced and 6G systems has been detailed. As for the former, it is not expected that future 3GPP releases will cover novel use cases, even though particular attention is being devoted to advanced Multicast and Broadcast Services. With respect to 6G, it is expected that a significant breakthrough in technologies and architectures will lead to the creation of a fully connected world around the following concepts: i) **digital twinning of systems**, with sensors and actuators that can tightly synchronise the domains to achieve digital twins of cities, factories, or even our bodies; ii) **connected intelligence**, with the network serving as the key infrastructure with trusted Artificial Intelligence (AI) functions managing virtual representations in the digital domain; and iii) **immersive communications**, where high-resolution visual/spatial, tactile/haptic, and other sensory data can be exchanged with high throughput and low latency to create an immersive experience of being somewhere else.

The envisaged services and architecture solutions are summarised in Table 10.

Table 10. Envisaged NTN service and architecture evolutions.

	5G	5G-Advanced	6G
Service evolution	eMBB-s mMTC-s <ul style="list-style-type: none"> global NB-IoT/mMTC coverage smart good tracking HRC-s <ul style="list-style-type: none"> governmental services emergency management remote control/monitoring of critical infrastructures 	Broadcast and Multicast services via satellite	Ultra MBB Immersive Communications Ultra-Critical Communications Ubiquitous MTC and Ultra massive connectivity Network Sensing Artificial Intelligence
Architecture evolution	Transparent payload in FR1 and FR2	Regenerative payloads Relay-based architecture NTN-TN Multi-Connectivity	3D ML-MO-MB architecture
Deployment scenarios	Handheld outdoor terminals with direct connectivity below 10 GHz	Handheld outdoor Handheld outdoor, Public Safety Mobile platforms and building mounted VSAT	Handheld light indoor Handheld outdoor Vehicle or drone mounted

In line with the service and architecture evolutions, a set of target performance requirements has been proposed for the different deployment scenarios included in Table 10.

Finally, a set of candidate technologies and techniques has been identified and detailed for both 5G-Advanced and 6G systems. Table 11 and Table 12 summarise the main benefits and challenges for candidate solutions in 5G-Advanced and 6G systems, respectively.

Table 11. Summary of advantages and challenges for 5G-A candidate technologies.

Technique/technology	Pros	Cons
MU-MIMO: standalone NTN node	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improved data rate - improved reliability - robustness to the UE speed - reduced latency with OBBF and DBC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - signalling overhead, in particular for CSI-based algorithms - security for location-based algorithms - on-board computational complexity for DBC - CSI or location aging due to the satellite movement (in particular for LEO systems) - traffic-based scheduling
MC and CA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improved data rate - improved reliability - support for high speed UEs - reduced latency achieved by operating at layers above PHY 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - adaptation of the F1 interface required with regenerative payloads - synchronisation and buffering, in particular for NTN-TN MC/CA - satellites movement and handover - scheduler complexity/out-of-order packets
Beam management and BWP association	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - slightly improved data rate by means of more efficient beam resource allocation - improved reliability and support for high speed UEs by means of more efficient handover procedures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - applicable to option 3 only (multiple beams per cell) - system capacity issues
Duplexing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improved data rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - signalling and guard bands/times overhead - increased guard times in NTN scenarios compared to TN
L-band and higher frequency bands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improved data rate - improved reliability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - spectrum harmonisation in terms of regulations and adjacent channel coexistence - possible challenges related to FDD operations in FR2 - identification of 3GPP-compliant parameters for PHY and TX/RX characteristics
User Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improved data rate - improved reliability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - coexistence to be assessed - TX/RX characteristics to be defined such that EMF constraints are met
NTN-TN and NTN-NTN mobility and service continuity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improved data rate - improved reliability - support for high speed UEs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - latency and synchronisation challenges with NGSO platforms - procedures adaptations due to potentially frequent handover - potentially large overhead in signalling for handover measurements - synchronisation, in particular in the NTN-TN scenario

Table 12. Summary of advantages and challenges for 6G candidate technologies.

Technique/technology	Pros	Cons
MU-MIMO: multiple NTN nodes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improved data rate - improved reliability - robustness to the UE speed - reduced latency with OBBF and DBC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - signalling overhead, in particular for CSI-based algorithms, also related to the swarm management - synchronisation - security for location-based algorithms - on-board computational complexity for DBC - CSI or location aging due to the satellite movement (in particular for LEO systems) - traffic-based scheduling
Waveform constraints and design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improved data rate - improved reliability - robustness to the UE speed, in particular with OTFS and OFDM variants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - introduction of a new or modified waveform compared to 5G CP-OFDM - modulator/demodulator complexity - feasibility study required for OTFS in NTN
AI/ML	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improved data rate - improved reliability - robustness to the UE speed - reduced latency - improved positioning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - computational complexity when training the network on-board - system overhead when training the network on-ground - difficulty in obtaining real observations for the network training
ISL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improved data rate - improved reliability - robustness to the UE speed - reduced latency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - regulatory aspects related to ISLs to be addressed in WRC-23 - synchronisation and signalling - support for non-persistent F1 interfaces when functional split is implemented - assessment of the NR-NTN procedures in the presence of ISLs
NOMA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improved data rate - improved reliability - robustness to the UE speed, since no CSI is required 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - increased complexity at the receiver - challenges related to power-based techniques, in particular for UEs in the same beam
RIS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improved data rate - improved reliability - improved positioning for indoor scenarios via NTN 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - signalling and synchronisation - computational complexity - feasibility assessment to be performed from scratch

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THE EAGER PROJECT

This document summarises the initial outcomes of the **EAGER (tEchnologies And techniques for satcom beyond 5G nEtwoRks)** Project, funded by the European Space Agency (ESA). This Study is coordinated by the University of Bologna and the Partners are: Thales Alenia Space Italia, Thales Alenia Space France, Magister Solutions, and Martel Innovate.

Leveraging the soon to be finalized Rel. 17 Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) standardization framework, the EAGER project aims at **researching innovative technologies and techniques targeting highly efficient and deeply integrated satellite networks in beyond 5G cellular systems**. The objectives are:

- To **evaluate and adopt discarded solutions** or use cases, including, *e.g.*, MIMO techniques, advanced payload with digital beamforming and active antennas, AI/ML techniques, low PAPR waveforms, handheld direct access for broadband communications with VLEO constellations, mMTC, self-driving car services and V2X applications, etc.
- To **identify and evaluate novel concepts** (both in the waveform and in the network domain, as well as in the space and ground segment technologies).
- To **develop the necessary software or analytical tools** in order to properly assess the performance of the most promising techniques and technologies.

Both **mid- and long-term satellite network solutions are being targeted** with a focus on solutions providing **mobile broadband** services as follows:

- **Mid-term:** the Study will select and evaluate the most relevant candidate features that were de-prioritized from Rel. 18, such as the support of UEs without GNSS, beam management and bandwidth part (BWP) association enhancements, carrier aggregation, coordinated transmission, asynchronous multi connectivity etc.
- **Long-term:** the Study will
 - Undertake some preliminary studies on versatile radio protocols able to cope with terrestrial and satellite propagation channel impairments and constraints thanks to low PAPR, as well as AI/ML techniques.
 - Carry out some feasibility study and trade-offs on a novel VLEO-based network infrastructure providing mobile broadband services to small terminals.

To this aim, the project will also **develop some NTN link/capacity/system level simulation tools** and use them to assess the performance gain of the considered techniques.

More information can be found on the project website (<https://www.eagerproject.eu>) and on the following social media channels:

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eager-project/>
- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/eagersatcom>

Stay tuned!

